
Making Sense of Consent with Knowledge Graphs

Anelia Malcheva Kurteva

Semantic Technology Institute (STI)
Department of Computer Science
University of Innsbruck

A thesis submitted for the degree of
Doctor of Philosophy in
Computer Science

Supervisor:

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Anna Fensel

Co-supervisor:

Univ.-Prof. Dr. Dieter Fensel

© Copyright Anelia Kurteva
The material in this thesis is protected by copyright law.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my gratitude to my supervisors Assoc. Prof. Dr. Anna Fensel and Univ.-Prof. Dr. Dieter Fensel and the whole STI Innsbruck team for the warm welcome in the University of Innsbruck. Thank you Anna for seeing my potential and for giving me the opportunity to do research in your team. I would also like to thank my fellow researchers Tek Raj Chhetri, Sareh Aghaei for always being up for thought provoking and entertaining discussions and Harshvardhan J Pandit for giving me a kick-start after reading his thesis and always answering my GDPR and cookie questions.

On a personal note, ab imo pectore, I would like to thank my family for always supporting me no matter what. Nothing would have been possible without you. Thank you Bernadette and Kaya for the support through the past few years. I learned a lot from both of you. Finally, I sincerely thank an important person who encouraged and supported me before I had my first publications and made me look forward to doing research.

Anelia M Kurteva

"I've learned that people will forget what you said, people will forget what you did, but people will never forget how you made them feel." - Maya Angelou

Abstract

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [1], which came into effect in May 2018, triggered a major technological shift towards greater transparency in data sharing [2]. An emphasis has been put on the rights of individuals, especially European citizens, regarding their personal data sharing. Despite the fact that data sharing has been a widely researched topic for years, there is a lack of solutions that enable the transparent implementation of consent in an easily understandable manner for both humans and machines in compliance with GDPR. This thesis presents a knowledge graph-based approach for consent representation and implementation that supports machines and humans in making sense of consent through its entire life-cycle. This is achieved by combining approaches from the computer science and behavioral change fields and by considering the comprehension needs of both humans and machines.

This thesis demonstrates the feasibility of the approach through its successful adoption and implementation in two industrial data sharing use cases in the smart cities and insurance domains from the smashHit and CampaNeo projects. The main objectives of this work are to use knowledge graphs to semantically represent the life-cycle of informed consent and to visually represent it to individuals in effort to increase legal awareness of the significance of consent [3]. The visualisations place emphasis on the pre- and post-consent stages, including how to request consent in an informed manner and what happens to one's data after consent is given. Incentives, in the form of gamification, are further used to overcome issues such as blindly given consent and to raise the consent rates.

Contents

List of Tables	xi
List of Figures	xii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Introduction and Motivation	1
1.1.1 Use Case 1: Traffic and Smart City Services	8
1.1.2 Use Case 2: Insurance Data Services	9
1.2 Problem Statement	10
1.3 Research Questions	12
1.4 Thesis Proposal	12
1.5 Hypotheses	13
1.6 Research Goals	14
1.7 Scientific Contribution	14
1.8 Thesis Outline	23
2 Related Work	25
2.1 Basics and Definitions	25
2.2 Semantic Models for Consent	29
2.2.1 Consent and Data Management Model (CDMM)	30
2.2.2 GConsent	30
2.2.3 Privacy Ontology (PrOnto)	31
2.2.4 Legal Complaint Ontology to Preserve Privacy for the Internet of Things (LloPY)	31
2.2.5 Business Process Re-engineering and Functional Toolkit for GDPR Compliance (BPR4GDPR)	32
2.2.6 SPECIALs Usage Policy Language (SPL)	32
2.2.7 Collaborative Privacy Knowledge Management Ontol- ogy for the Internet of Things (ColPri)	33

2.2.8	Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV)	33
2.2.9	Summary	34
2.3	Semantic Models for Sensor Data	36
2.3.1	OntoSensor	36
2.3.2	Sensor Model Language (SensorML)	36
2.3.3	Ontonym - Sensor	37
2.3.4	Semantic Sensor Network Ontology (SSN)	37
2.3.5	Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (SOSA)	38
2.3.6	Summary	38
2.4	Semantic Models for Data Sharing	39
2.5	Semantic Models for Provenance	40
2.6	Summary	41
2.7	Human Behaviour and Consent	42
2.8	Consent Visualisation	46
2.8.1	Data Track	47
2.8.2	The GDPR-compliant and Usable Privacy Dashboard	48
2.8.3	The CoRe and CURE UIs	49
2.8.4	TransparencyVis	51
2.8.5	Summary	53
2.9	Projects Addressing GDPR and Consent	55
2.9.1	Mining and Reasoning with Legal Texts (MIREL) (January 2016-December 2019)	56
2.9.2	Scalable Policy-aware Linked Data Architecture for Pri- vacy, Transparency and Compliance (SPECIAL)(January 2017-December 2019)	56
2.9.3	Cyber-Physical Social Systems to Support City-wide Infrastructures (CitySPIN) (October 2017-March 2020)	57
2.9.4	Data Governance Framework for Supporting GDPR (DEFEND)(July 2018-March 2021)	58
2.9.5	SOLID (August 2016-ongoing)	58
2.9.6	Summary	59
3	Approach and Methodology	60
3.1	Approach	60
3.2	Methodology	63
4	Implementation	68
4.1	Step 1: Ontology Engineering	69
4.1.1	Consent	71
4.1.2	Data Processing	72
4.1.3	Agent and Role	73

4.1.4	Data Source and Resource	74
4.1.5	Location and Time	74
4.2	Step 2: UI Design and Implementation (Including Gamification)	75
4.2.1	First Iteration of the CampaNeo Consent Request UI	76
4.2.2	Second Iteration of the CampaNeo Consent Request UI	79
4.2.3	Gamification	81
4.3	Step 3: KG Construction	84
4.3.1	Create Consent Instances	85
4.3.2	View Consent Instances	88
4.3.3	Revoke Consent	89
4.4	Step 4: KG Data Flow Visualisation (Post-Consent)	91
4.4.1	First Iteration of the KG Data Flow Visualisation	91
4.4.2	Second Iteration of the KG Data Flow Visualisation	92
4.5	KG for GDPR Compliance	97
4.6	Summary	98
5	Evaluation	99
5.1	Evaluation of smashHitCore	99
5.1.1	Evaluation Set Up	99
5.1.2	Results	100
5.2	Evaluation of the CampaNeo Consent Request UI	102
5.2.1	Evaluation Set Up	102
5.2.2	Results	103
5.3	Evaluation of the Post-Consent KG Visualisation	109
5.3.1	Evaluation Set Up	109
5.3.2	Results	112
5.4	Summary	114
6	Conclusions and Outlook	116
6.1	Lessons Learned	117
6.1.1	Consent Request	117
6.1.2	Consent Comprehension	119
6.1.3	Consent Decision	121
6.1.4	Consent Use	122
6.1.5	Consent Management	123
6.2	Outlook	124
	Appendices	126
	Appendix A Dictionary	127

Appendix B	Abbreviations	133
Appendix C	Thesis Results	134
Appendix D	Utilised Technologies	135
Appendix E	SPARQL Query: Display Consent Instances	136
Appendix F	Post-Consent KG Visualisation Evaluation Tasks	138
Appendix G	CampaNeo Evaluation Survey Results	139
Appendix H	Post-Consent Evaluation Survey Results	157
References		171

List of Tables

2.1	Overview of Existing Semantic Models for Consent from [2]	35
2.2	Overview of Existing Consent Visualisation Tools [4]	54
3.1	Functional and Non-functional Requirements	64
3.2	Implementation Steps and Relevant Publications	67
5.1	Evaluation of smashHitCore with Competency Questions [5]	101
5.2	CURE vs CampaNeo Usability Task Comparison [4]	107
A.1	GDPR [1] Dictionary of Legal Terms	127
B.1	Abbreviations	133
C.1	Thesis Results	134
D.1	Utilised Technologies	135
F.1	Post-Consent KG Visualisation Evaluation Tasks	138

List of Figures

1.1	Sample Campaign in CampaNeo	7
1.2	Use Case 1: Consent for Sensor Data Sharing in Smart Cities (Traffic Detection)	9
1.3	Smart City Domains	11
2.1	The Data Track Tool by Angulo et al. [6]	48
2.2	The Privacy Dashboard by Raschke et al. [7]	49
2.3	The CoRe UI by Drozd and Kirrane [8]	51
2.4	The CURE UI by Drozd and Kirrane [9]	52
2.5	The TransparencyVis UI by Schufrin et al. [10]	53
3.1	The Life-Cicle of Consent by Kurteva et al. [2]	61
3.2	Methodology Overview	66
4.1	Knowledge Graph-based Consent Visualisation System's Layers	69
4.2	Overview of smashHitCore	70
4.3	Overview of the Class Consent and Relevant Consent Concepts in smashHitCore	71
4.4	Overview of the Class Data Processing in smashHitCore	72
4.5	Overview of the classes Agent and Role from smashHitCore	73
4.6	CampaNeo UI (1): Campaign Overview	76
4.7	CampaNeo UI (1): Campaign Details	77
4.8	CampaNeo UI (1): Consent Confirmation	78
4.9	CampaNeo UI (1): Active Campaigns	79
4.10	CampaNeo UI (2): Main Page	80
4.11	CampaNeo UI (2): Campaign Details	81
4.12	CampaNeo UI (2): Main Page Active Campaigns	82
4.13	CampaNeo UI (2): Data Sharing Gamification Element	82
4.14	CampaNeo UI (2): Shop Page	83

4.15	CampaNeo UI (2): Leaders' Board	83
4.16	Data Flow: From UI to KG	85
4.17	New Consent Instance Insert Query Result	88
4.18	View All Consent Information (Tabular Format)	89
4.19	Revoke Consent (Status Update Query Result)	90
4.20	Current Campaign (Overview Visualisation)	92
4.21	Current Campaign (Detailed Visualisation)	92
4.22	KG Visualisation System Architecture [11]	93
4.23	KG Data Flow Visualisation UI	94
4.24	Campaign Data Flow Details	95
4.25	Automated GDPR Compliance System Architecture [12]	97
5.1	Consent UI and Gamification Evaluation Flow [4]	103
5.2	CampaNeo UI: Success Rate of Tasks [4]	106
5.3	Consent and GDPR Comprehension: (a) Evaluation Results of Users' Consent Comprehension and (b) Users' Confidence in Knowledge of GDPR.	107
5.4	Gamification Results: (a) Overall Incentives' Satisfaction and (b) Motivation to participate in Campaigns (1-Most Disagree- able, 4-Most Agreeable).	108
5.5	UI Design Survey Feedback	109
5.6	KG Visualisation Evaluation Flow	111
5.7	Data Sharing User Evaluation Before using the UI.	114
5.8	Data Sharing User Evaluation After using the UI.	114
E.1	SPARQL Query: Display Consent Instances	137

This chapter presents an overview of consent for sensor data sharing in the smart cities and insurance domains from both human and machine standpoints. Relevant legal and technical concepts, as well as semantic technologies used later in this thesis, are also presented. The chapter also describes the two key use cases and the challenges that motivated this work and the research questions that will be addressed. Definitions of all GDPR-related legal terms and abbreviations used in this work can be found in table A.1 and table B.1 in the appendix.

1.1 Introduction and Motivation

In May 2018, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [1] came into force and introduced new requirements regarding the use of the personal data of European Union (EU) citizens that need to be met. According to Article 4 (1) of GDPR, any data that can be traced back to a specific individual is viewed as personal data [2]. In order for this data to be lawfully processed under the GDPR, individual's consent is needed. Consent, one of the six GDPR bases for the lawful data processing of EU citizens's data, is defined as *"any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data*

subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her" (GDPR [1], Art. 4(11)). The other five bases are performance of a contract, a legitimate interest, a vital interest, a legal requirement, and a public interest (GDPR [1], Art. 6). The research work presented in this thesis focuses specifically on consent.

To be specific, GDPR stands for consent that is informed. Having a consent request that simply asks for consent in the form of a "Yes" or "No" question is not sufficient for compliant data sharing to begin under the GDPR. In order to have informed consent, upon a consent request, individuals should be made aware of (i) the type of data that will be shared, (ii) the identity of the data controller, processor ect., (iii) the specific time duration of the consent and (iv) the purpose for the consent request (GDPR [1], Art. 4, 6, 7, 8). Further, as discussed in [2], individuals should be made aware of their right to withdraw their consent at any time (also known as "*the right to be forgotten*" (GDPR [1], Rec. 66)).

From a technological point of view, the acceptance of GDPR has caused a major shift in how personal data is handled [3]. GDPR applies to all companies that deal with the personal data of EU citizens, no matter their size and calls for transparency and traceability [13]. Achieving and providing both at every organization level, from low-level data processing to data collection itself is a challenge faced by many. In an organisation, data can be spread between multiple silos (e.g. departments, databases, processes). Locating informed consent information such as a consent decision (given or not given) can be time-consuming and in some cases might not be possible

due to privacy and security metrics (e.g. authorisation and access protocols that are in place in most corporations). The issue further deepens, in cases such as smart cities (i.e. "*cities using technological solutions to improve the management and efficiency of the urban environment*"¹), where data is simultaneously collected, accessed and modified by multiple devices. A smart city, can have several interlinked domains such as transport, healthcare, insurance and smart homes, which depend on cross-domain data sharing. Examples of such cities are London, Singapore, Helsinki. New technologies that support the transparency and traceability of personal data processing and that preserve individuals privacy are in demand [4] [2]. The main challenge that many face when modelling and managing informed consent is its representation in an interpretable and comprehensible way to both machines and humans.

The Semantic Web field has set as one of its main goals the interpretability of information between humans and machines [14] [15] [16]. Further, the Semantic Web enables a cost-effective way for humans to record, share and discover knowledge in a unified manner with the help of semantics [17]. Semantic technologies such as the Resource Description Framework (RDF)², RDF Schema (RDFs)³ and the Web Ontology Language (OWL)⁴ allow one to add meaning via the relationships that exist between things. OWL and RDFs can be used to create more complex semantic structures such as schemas and ontologies, which provide a formal explicit conceptualisation of the world [18]. With the help of ontologies, human ideas, thoughts and events can be semantically enriched and translated into machine-readable statements and rules.

¹https://ec.europa.eu/info/euregionalandurbandevelopment/topics/citiesandurban-development/cityinitiatives/smartcities_en

²<https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

³<https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/>

⁴<https://www.w3.org/2001/sw/wiki/OWL>

As a result, a machine can perform better and faster search, filtering, ranking, personalisation and contextualisation [19–27]. A semantic technology that is gaining popularity within the data and knowledge management fields is the knowledge graph (KG). Despite its long history, which dates back to 1972, the term KG came into focus in 2012 after the announcement of the Google KG⁵. Many definitions for a KG exist. For example, KGs are viewed as *“very large semantic nets that integrate various and heterogenous information sources to represent knowledge about certain domains”* (Fensel et al. [17]).

A comprehensive survey on the topic of KGs is presented by Hogan et al. [28]. Some of the most well-known open KGs (i.e. open-access) are DBpedia⁶, Wikidata⁷, YAGO⁸, Freebase⁹, and NELL¹⁰. In addition, private or also known as enterprise KGs have been built in many organizations to support knowledge management [29]. For example, Facebooks entity graph, Cyc¹¹, Google’s⁵ and Yahoo’s [30] KGs. With regards to consent and its comprehension, as mentioned in [3], KGs can support explainability and can provide both traceability and transparency two principal pillars of GDPR [31]. The use of semantic technology in various domains such as mobility [32], law [31], energy [33], tourism [17] and more has undoubtedly shown to be beneficial to machines. Despite their wide application, most KGs are build by experts, who have deep understanding of the Semantic Web field. When

⁵<https://googleblog.blogspot.com/2012/05/introducing-knowledge-graph-things-not.html>

⁶<https://www.dbpedia.org>

⁷https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page

⁸<https://yago-knowledge.org>

⁹<http://www.freebase.com>

¹⁰<http://rtw.ml.cmu.edu/rtw/kbbrowser/>

¹¹<http://www.cyc.com>

it comes to consent, however, it is yet to be explored how KGs can be used to assist the comprehension of non-experts [3]. A discussion on the topic of successfully deploying Semantic Web technologies and the main challenges that users face is also presented by Heath et al. [34].

From a human perspective, research such as [35] [36] [4] has shown that individuals are unaware of what giving consent implies and the implications that follow. For example, giving consent for vehicle sensor data sharing to a vehicle manufacturer for maintenance purposes, who then share the sensor data with an insurance company [2]. In such cases, as presented in the next sections, the outcome might not be as beneficial for the vehicle owner as it is for the insurer when accidents occur.

One of the most common ways to request consent online is via consent forms, for example, cookie dialogs [37]. However, in most cases, the presented information that is needed for informed consent is missing or is written in a legalese (i.e. legal jargon), which does not ease individuals' comprehension [38]. Instead, negative emotions such as confusion and irritation can arise and can cause individuals to give consent in order to be done with the request. Bechman [35] defines this behaviour of unawareness of what consent implies as a culture of blind consent. Further, biases stemming from one's culture, upbringing, education and personal beliefs can play a role in how information is perceived. Following GDPR's requirements for informed consent does not guarantee comprehension in individuals [4] [2]. While too little information (in textual format) might not be informative enough, too much can lead to an information overload [39]. A way to minimise the presence of textual information is via visualisations such as icons, graphs and images,

which are better perceived by humans [40–45]. In addition to supporting the comprehension of consent, graphical visualisations can also be used to convey information regarding the implications of consent for data sharing [11] [2]. Behavioural decision-making theory [46] provides a valuable insight of human behaviour, namely on how decisions are made and how environmental stimuli can affect them [47] [48]. External stimuli such as incentives [49] can be found everywhere around us in any form. Research [50–53] has shown that incentives in the form of gamification [54] can be used as additional motivation for individuals during decision making, to attract attention and to increase participation. As discussed through this work, incentives can help to attract ones attention and raise the consenting rate [4].

In conclusion, semantic technology, namely KGs can be used to solve the issue of implementing informed consent in a comprehensible way for both machines and humans [2] [4] [11]. This thesis explores the semantic representation of consent for both humans and machines. While a semantic model such as an ontology is enough for a machine to comprehend the world, it might not be enough for humans, especially non-experts (i.e. individuals with no knowledge of the Semantic Web) [4]. A new way of presenting the information visually to individuals that is compliant with GDPR, supports one’s comprehension, does not result in information overload and motivates one to give consent and become aware of its meaning, is needed.

Finally, the research that this thesis outlines is based on the Campaigno¹²(FFG grant agreement ID: 873839) and smashHit¹³(H2020 grant agreement ID: 871477) projects, and the use cases presented in sections 1.1.1 and

¹²<https://projekte.ffg.at/projekt/3314668>

¹³<https://smashhit.eu>

Campaign Name: Roads of Innsbruck
Campaign Id: 29376661
Purpose: The Tyrolean government wants to examine which roads of Innsbruck are heavily used in order to determine if further investment is needed
Data of Interest: GPS data from car drivers in the area of Innsbruck and up to 15 km away
Data Processing: Collection, anonymisation
Storage Location: [Kufstein](#)
Start Date: 20/10/2020
End Date: 01/11/2020
Data Controller: Volkswagen
Medium: Online application

Figure 1.1: Sample Campaign in CampaNeo

1.1.2. Both projects focus on consent for data sharing as defined by GDPR. With the help of campaigns, CampaNeo plans to develop an open platform for both corporate and public institutions to gather, process and analyse vehicle sensor data. (figure 1.1). In the context of CampaNeo, a campaigns present individuals with an informed consent request for a specific type of vehicle sensor data such as Global Positioning System (GPS) (latitude, longitude), fuel, mileage that will be analysed with the help of machine learning for purposes such as detection of driving behaviour, finding of driver efficiency scores and anomaly detection [2]. While CampaNeo focuses on data analytics, smashHit's focus is on consent management in compliance with GDPR. The objective of smashHit is to assure trusted and secure sharing of data streams from both personal and industrial platforms, needed to build sectorial and cross-sectorial services, by establishing a framework for processing of data owner consent and legal rules and effective contracting, as well as joint security and privacy preserving mechanisms [55].

1.1.1 Use Case 1: Traffic and Smart City Services

Use case 1 (UC1) (figure 1.2) focuses on the mobility domain in smart cities. From data owner perspective, the main challenges in this use case are the lack of awareness of what smart cities are, how data is shared between the entities in them and how one can have control over it. From a technical perspective, the challenge is the management of consent itself. Specifically, its informed request and storage. Other challenges, presented in UC1 and UC2 are with regards to simplifying the consent request process and increasing users' motivation to consent (e.g. how to make people consent as much as possible without payments or other expensive explicit measures). In UC1, vehicle owners are asked for consent to share sensor data while driving. The sensor data is collected and analysed for various purposes such as traffic or CO₂ emission detection, monitoring of the road conditions. The vehicle sensor data can also be used to analyse the condition of the vehicle itself. For example, the collection of sensor data about the vehicles mileage, emergency and anti-lock brakes, steering wheel, etc. The result of such analysis can help predict possible vehicle malfunction and accidents. This use case is part of both CampaNeo and smashHit, is supported by several organizations, namely Volkswagen AG¹⁴, Infotripla¹⁵, Forum Virium Helsinki¹⁶ and is to be realised at two locations - Hannover and Helsinki.

¹⁴<https://www.volkswagenag.com/de.html>

¹⁵<https://infotripla.fi>

¹⁶<https://forumvirium.fi>

Figure 1.2: Use Case 1: Consent for Sensor Data Sharing in Smart Cities (Traffic Detection)

1.1.2 Use Case 2: Insurance Data Services

Use Case 2 (UC2), which is part of the smashHit project and is supported by Volkswagen AG and LexisNexis ¹⁷, focuses on the use of connected car data in the insurance sector. The two main challenges that are encountered by far are the lack of trust by consumers regarding the use of their data and the complexity for the consumer to provide the consent required under GDPR. For example, vehicle sensor data from UC1 can be analysed and then used for the estimation of liability, property and personal/life insurances. In the case of insurance in a smart city, the task becomes more challenging as many factors can affect insurers' decisions [2]. For example, in cases such as a smart home fire or burglary insurances, an insurance company might need access to the performance reports (i.e. data analysis) of several appliances in the smart home in order to be able to provide a reasonable insurance quotes.

¹⁷<https://www.lexisnexis.com/en-us/home.page>

1.2 Problem Statement

The notion of consent has existed for long before the acceptance of the GDPR. However, there are still challenges regarding its representation, management and comprehension, especially in the technology, smart city and insurance domains where a standard solution has not been set out yet [3].

As discussed in [3], in smart cities, data is spread across different silos (figure 1.3) and can be used for different purposes by different entities simultaneously. Consent should be implemented in a way that does not disrupt data flow between silos while remaining GDPR compliant [3] [2]. The work in [56] has shown that the majority of individuals have only a vague idea of smart cities and informed consent. Further, research has shown that, if not asked explicitly for permission, most individuals are unaware that their personal data might be shared [4] [11] [3]. More often, the consent for data sharing is presented in textual format and is written in complex legal language. Instead of easing and informing individuals about their consent rights, it can have the opposite effect. It can result in information overload [39] and individuals providing consent without understanding or perhaps even not reading the presented data sharing policies [57] [3].

The already available consent ontologies (see chapter 2) differ in the level of details that are modelled. Most focus on representing semantically consent but not the specific sensor data and the processing related to it [2]. In order to be reused for consent life-cycle modelling, *"the existing ontologies need to be extended so that different domains such as transport, education, security, retail, energy, etc., which are present in a smart city are modelled"* [2].

Although, KGs are becoming a more prominent technology in research,

Figure 1.3: Smart City Domains

their capabilities to implement consent through its whole life-cycle are yet to be explored. In addition, as consent must be given prior to data sharing, the developed technological solutions should "equally considers the needs of both humans and machines when consent is implemented" [3] and should provide "a transparent view into the life cycle of one's consent and one's legal rights" [3].

1.3 Research Questions

The main objective of this thesis, as presented also in [3], is to present a semantic KG-based approach for consent representation and management, which helps machines and humans to make sense of consent. The main research question that will be answered is :

How to represent informed consent with KGs in a way that supports its comprehension by both humans and machines?

Further, based on the notion that machines and humans comprehend the world in different ways (i.e. humans interpret visual/graphical representations of information better) the following sub-question arises:

How to explain informed consent to individuals in an understandable way with the help of visualisations?

Finally, following behavioural change theories, which focus on processes such as human decision making and the different tools (e.g. incentives) that can be used to support comprehension, the following sub-question will be answered as well:

Can incentives help raise one's legal awareness?

1.4 Thesis Proposal

The main contributions of this thesis are (i) an approach (see [12] [5]) for representing informed consent for sensor data sharing in compliance with GDPR with KGs, (ii) an implementation of the approach [12], which supports its synchronisation across multiple domains (e.g. mobility and insurance), (iii) an application [4] with a user interface (UI) for consent management,

which complies with GDPR and assists individuals in granting and revoking consent, (iv) an approach for graphically visualising KG data flows that helps individuals better comprehend data sharing and consent, and (v) increased consent rates as a result of the adopted gamification mechanism [4].

The developed solution that provides these functionalities is based on a legal GDPR KG focused on consent, which is visualised via a UI. The KG itself is based on the smashHitCore¹⁸ [5] consent ontology built for the smashHit project. smashHitCore is a GDPR-compliant ontology for secure and controlled sharing of personal and industrial data. The UIs (see [4] and [11]) is aimed at improving ones comprehension of consent with the help of (i) visualisation of informed consent requests, (ii) visualisation of what happens after consent is given and (iii) incentives, namely gamification. Human behavioural theory [58], UI and User Experience (UX) [59] design principles have been taken into account when developing the UI. Feedback regarding the developed solution is obtained by crowd-sourcing both expert and non-expert individuals.

1.5 Hypotheses

Based on the problem statement presented in section 1.2, the following hypotheses are defined:

Hypothesis 1: Representing informed consent with KGs can successfully support the sensor data sharing between multiple silos in a smart city.

Hypothesis 2: Visualisation of a KG improves individuals' comprehension of consent.

¹⁸<https://smashhiteu.github.io/smashHitCore/>

Hypothesis 3: Incentives increase users' willingness to consent and assist in raising individuals' awareness of consent.

1.6 Research Goals

The following research goals are derived to address the research objective that is presented in the introduction of this thesis and are further aligned with the hypothesis presented in the previous section.

Goal 1: Define the life-cycle of consent (from request to revocation).

Goal 2: Define a schema for a KG, which is able to represent informed consent through its whole life-cycle in a smart city environment, specifically in the domains of mobility and insurance.

Goal 3: Develop an incentive mechanism based on gamification that motivates data subjects to give consent and helps raise their awareness.

Goal 4: Support and improving individual's comprehension of consent with graphical visualisations. This includes both the UI and the visualisation of the data flow after consent is given.

Goal 5: Provide a proof of concept by developing a KG-based UI for consent management.

1.7 Scientific Contribution

This section presents the main scientific publications that this thesis is based on. In addition, important parts of this research were also presented in newsletters and presentations given at international conferences.

Scientific publications relevant to this research:

1. A. Kurteva, Implementing Informed Consent with Knowledge Graphs, **European Semantic Web Conference (ESWC)**, pp. 155-164, Springer, Cham., https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80418-3_28, 2021.

Abstract: The GDPR legislation has brought to light one's rights and has highlighted the importance of consent, which has caused a major shift in how data processing and sharing are handled. Data sharing has been a popular research topic for many years, however, a unified solution for the transparent implementation of consent, in compliance with GDPR that could be used as a standard, has not been presented yet. This research proposes a solution for implementing informed consent for sensor data sharing in compliance with GDPR with semantic technology, namely KGs. The main objectives are to model the life cycle of informed consent (i.e. the request, comprehension, decision and use of consent) with KGs so that it is easily interpretable by machines, and to graphically visualise it to individuals in order to raise legal awareness of what it means to consent and the implications that follow.

2. A. Kurteva, T. R. Chhetri, H. J.Pandit, A. Fensel, Consent through The Lens of Semantics: State of The Art survey and Best Practices, **Semantic Web** (Preprint), pp. 1-27., <https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-210438>, 2021.

Abstract: The acceptance of the GDPR legislation in 2018 started a new technological shift towards achieving transparency. GDPR put focus on the concept of informed consent applicable for data processing, which led to an increase of the responsibilities regarding data sharing

for both end users and companies. This paper presents a literature survey of existing solutions that use semantic technology for implementing consent. The main focus is on ontologies, how they are used for consent representation and for consent management in combination with other technologies such as blockchain. We also focus on visualisation solutions aimed at improving individuals consent comprehension. Finally, based on the overviewed state of the art we propose best practices for consent implementation.

3. A. Kurteva, T. R. Chhetri, R. Hilscher, A. Tauqeer, A. Fensel, K. Nagorny, A. Correia, A. Zilverberg, S. Schestakov, T. Funke, E. Demidova, The smashHitCore Ontology for GDPR-compliant Data sharing in Smart Cities, **Journal of Web Semantics** (In Review), 2022.

Abstract: The adoption of GDPR has resulted in a significant shift in how the data of European Union citizens is handled. A variety of data sharing challenges in scenarios such as smart cities have arisen, especially, when attempting to semantically represent GDPR legal bases, such as consent, contracts and the data types and specific data sources related to them. Many ontologies that model GDPR exist, however, they focus mainly on consent. In order to represent other GDPR bases such as contracts, multiple ontologies need to be reused and combined. To solve this challenge, we present the smashHitCore ontology, which provides a unified and coherent model for both consent and contracts, as well as the sensor data and data processing associated with them, in one place. The ontology was developed in response to real-world data sharing use cases in the insurance and smart cities domains and has

been successfully utilised for performing automated GDPR compliance verification.

4. T. R. Chhetri, A. Kurteva, R. J. DeLong, R. Hilscher, K. Korte, A. Fensel, Data Protection by Design Tool for Automated GDPR Compliance Verification Based on Semantically Modeled Informed Consent, **Sensors, Special Issue Data Privacy, Security, and Trust in New Technological Trends**, vol 22(7):2763, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22072763>, 2022.

Abstract: The enforcement of the GDPR in May 2018 has led to a paradigm shift in data protection. Organisations face significant challenges, such as demonstrating compliance (or auditability) and automated compliance verification due to the complex and dynamic nature of consent, as well as the scale at which compliance verification must be performed. Furthermore, the GDPR's promotion of Data Protection by Design and industrial interoperability requirements has created a new technical challenges, as they require significant changes in the design and implementation of systems that handle personal data. We present a scalable Data Protection by Design tool for automated compliance verification and auditability based on informed consent that is modelled with a knowledge graph. Automated compliance verification is made possible by implementing a regulation-to-code process that translates GDPR regulations into well defined technical and organisational measures and ultimately software code. We demonstrate the effectiveness of the tool in the insurance and smart cities domains. We highlight ways in which our tool can be adapted to other domains.

5. A. Kurteva, H. D. Ribaupierre, Interface to Query and Visualise Definitions from a Knowledge Base. **International Conference on Web Engineering (ICWE)**, pp. 3-10, Springer, Cham, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-74296-6_1, 2021.

Abstract: Linked Data is at the core of the Web due to its ability to model real world entities, connect them via relationships and provide context, which could help to transform data into information and information into knowledge. For example, ontologies, which could be stored locally or could be made available to everyone online (e.g. the DBpedia knowledge base). However, both access and usage of Linked Data require individuals to have knowledge in the field of the Semantic Web. Many of the existing solutions are developed for specific use cases such as building and exploring ontologies visually and are aimed at expert users. The solutions that are aimed at non-experts are generic and, in most cases, a data visualisation is not available. In this paper, we present a web application with a user interface (UI), which combines features from applications for both expert and non-experts. The UI allows individuals with no previous knowledge of the Semantic Web to query the DBpedia knowledge base for definitions of a specific word and to view a graphical visualisation of the query results (the search keyword itself and concepts related to it).

6. C. Bless, L. Dtlinger, M. Kaltschmid, M. Reiter, A. Kurteva, A. J. Roa-Valverde, A. Fensel, Raising Awareness of Data Sharing Consent Through Knowledge Graph Visualisation, **SEMANTiCS**, In Further with Knowledge Graphs, pp. 44-57, IOS Press, <https://ebooks>.

iospress.nl/doi/10.3233/SSW210034, 2021.

Abstract: KGs facilitate systematic large-scale data analysis by providing both human and machine-readable structures, which can be shared across different domains and platforms. Nowadays, KGs can be used to standardise the collection and sharing of user information in many different sectors such as transport, insurance, smart cities and internet of things. Regulations such as the GDPR make sure that users are not taken advantage of when they share data. From a legal standpoint it is necessary to have the users consent to collect information. This consent is only valid if the user is aware about the information collected at all times. To increase this awareness, we present a KG visualisation approach, which informs users about the activities linked to their data sharing agreements, especially after they have already given their consent. To visualise the graph, we introduce a user-centred application which showcases sensor data collection and distribution to different data processors. Finally, we present the results of a user study conducted to find out whether this visualisation leads to more legal awareness and trust. We show that with our visualisation tool data sharing consent rates increase from 48% to 81.5%.

7. S. Rasmusen, M. Penz, S. Widauer, P. Nako, A. Kurteva, A. J. Roa-Valverde, A. Fensel, Raising Consent Awareness with Gamification and KGs: An Automotive Use Case, **International Journal of Semantic Web Information Systems (IJSWIS)**, vol 18(1), <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJSWIS.300820>, 2022.

Abstract: Consent is one of GDPRs lawful bases for data process-

ing and specific requirements for it apply. Consent should be specific, unambiguous and most of all informed. However, an informed consent request does not guarantee having individuals who are aware of what it means to consent and the implications that follow. Challenges such as information overload due to long privacy policies written in legal language and complex interface designs that cause consent fatigue, which results in blindly given consent, are still present. This paper presents a KG-based user interface for consent solicitation, which uses gamification to raise the legal awareness and ease individuals comprehension of consent. The KG models informed consent in a machine-readable format and provides a unified consent model to all entities involved in the data sharing process. The evaluation shows that with the help of gamification, the interface can raise individuals' average legal awareness to 92.86%.

8. A. Breitfuss, K. Errou, A. Kurteva, A. Fensel, Representing Emotions with Knowledge Graphs for Movie Recommendations, **Future Generation Computer Systems**, vol 125, pp. 715-725, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2021.06.001>, 2021.

Abstract: Consumption of media, and movies in particular, is increasing and is influenced by a number of factors. One important and overlooked factor that affects the media consumption choices is the emotional state of the user and the decision making based on it. To include this factor in movie recommendation processes, we propose a KG representing human emotions in the domain of movies. The KG has been built by extracting emotions out of pre-existing movie reviews

using machine learning techniques. To show how the KG can be used, a chatbot prototype has been developed. The chatbots reasoning mechanism derives movie recommendations for the user by combining the users emotions, which have been extracted from chat messages, with the KG. The developed approach for movie recommendations based on sentiment represented as a KG has been proven to be technically feasible, however, it requires more information about the emotions associated with the movies than currently available online.

9. T. R. Chhetri, A. Kurteva, J. G. Adigun, A. Fensel, Knowledge Graph Based Hard Drive Failure Prediction. **Sensors, Special Issue Production and Industrial Service Management in the Industry 4.0 Era: Digital Techniques in Operations**, vol 22(3):985, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22030985>, 2022.

Abstract: The hard drive is one of the important components of a computing system, and its failure can lead to both system failure and data loss. Therefore, the reliability of a hard drive is very important. Realising this importance, a number of studies have been conducted and many are still ongoing to improve hard drive failure prediction. Most of those studies rely solely on machine learning, and a few others on semantic technology. The studies based on machine learning, despite promising results, lack context-awareness such as how failures are related or what other factors, such as humidity, influence the failure of hard drives. Semantic technology, on the other hand, by means of ontologies and KGs (KGs), is able to provide the context-awareness that machine learning-based studies lack. However, the studies based on se-

semantic technology lack the advantages of machine learning, such as the ability to learn a pattern and make predictions based on learned patterns. Therefore, in this paper, leveraging the benefits of both machine learning (ML) and semantic technology, we present our study, KG-based hard drive failure prediction. The experimental results demonstrate that our proposed method achieves higher accuracy in comparison to the current state of the art.

Newsletters:

1. A. Fensel, A. Kurteva, Towards Better Modelling of Consent, **Osterreichischen Computer Gesellschaft (OCG)**, 2020, Available at <https://www.ocg.at/sites/ocg.at/files/medien/pdfs/OCG-Journal20-1-2.pdf>.
2. A. Kurteva, Feature of work in the **Eye on AI Newsletter**, March 2021.
3. A. Kurteva, A. Fensel, Enabling Interpretability in Smart Cities with KGs: Towards a Better Modelling of Consent, **IEEE Smart City**, June 2021, Available at <https://smartcities.ieee.org/newsletter/june-2021/enabling-interpretability-in-smart-cities-with-knowledge-graphs-towards-a-better-modelling-of-consent>.
4. A. Kurteva, Interface to Query and Visualise Definitions from a Knowledge Base, **DBpedia Newsletter**, Extended Community Edition, May 2021.

Presentations:

1. A. Kurteva, Representing and Managing Informed Consent with KGs, **Neo4j Online Developer Expo and Summit (NODES)**, 2020. Available at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358891345_Representing_and_Managing_Informed_User_Consent_with_Knowledge_Graphs_-_Neo4j_NODES_2020.
2. A. Kurteva, Implementing Informed Consent with KGs, **Connected Data World (CDW)**, 2021, Available at <https://2021.connected-data.world/talks/implementing-informed-consent-with-knowledge-graphs/>.
3. A. Kurteva, A. Tauqeer, A. Fensel, Data Sharing in smashHit: Making Consent and Contracts Interpretable with Knowledge Graphs, **Trusted Secure Data Sharing Space (TRUSTS)**, Workshop on Data Spaces and Semantic Interoperability, 2022, Available at <https://www.trusts-data.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/06-Data-sharing-in-smashHit-Making-consent-and-contracts-interpretable-with-knowledge-graphs.pdf>.

1.8 Thesis Outline

This thesis aims to provide and describe a new approach, based on KGs, which helps both machines and humans to make sense of consent for sensor data sharing in the smart cities and insurance domains. The presented approach considers the comprehension needs of both and presents a new application of incentives such as gamification (how they can be used when requesting consent).

The thesis is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2 - Related Work** provides an overview of existing ontologies for consent, consent visualisation based on semantics and human behaviour.
- **Chapter 3 - Approach and Methodology** presents the approach and the followed methodology for consent implementation with KGs.
- **Chapter 4 - Implementation** presents implementation details about the smashHitCore ontology, KG and their visualisations for consent request and after consent is given. The implementation of the gamification mechanism is discussed as well.
- **Chapter 5 - Evaluation** describes the selected evaluation of the presented approach, which is done by evaluating the solution developed based on it. Further, the chapter presents the results of each evaluation.
- **Chapter 6 - Discussions, Outlook and Conclusions** presents the outcomes of this research, its existing limitations and the achieved research goals. Further, it provides a discussion regarding possible future work, applications and directions.
- **Appendices** - presents additional sources of information for this thesis such as GDPR definitions (appendix A), abbreviations (appendix B), thesis results (appendix C), used technologies (appendix D), evaluation results (appendix G and H).

This chapter begins with basics and definitions of semantic technologies and other concepts such as consent implementation and management that are used in this work. Next, it presents a review of relevant work in the fields of (i) Semantic Web technologies, namely ontologies for informed consent, sensor data and data sharing, (ii) human behaviour when giving consent and (iii) consent visualisation. The main aim of this chapter is to present current state-of-the-art research, innovative solutions that have been proven efficient and their existing limitations - all in the context of informed consent representation (to both machines and humans).

2.1 Basics and Definitions

This section presents the main technology terms used in this thesis. Concepts such as "*ontology*" have a long history and many definitions exist while others such as "*consent management*", "*consent implementation*" and "*consent life-cycle*" are open to interpretation.

- **Ontologies** - "*A specification of a representational vocabulary for a shared domain of discourse definitions of classes, relations, functions, and other objects*" [18]. Ontologies are used "*to help data integration*

*when, for example, ambiguities may exist on the terms used in the different data sets, or when a bit of extra knowledge may lead to the discovery of new relationships.”*¹

- **Knowledge Graphs** - Many definitions for KGs exist. According to Ontotext², a KG *“represents a collection of interlinked descriptions of entities objects, events or concepts”*³. IBM defines them as semantic networks, which represent a *“network of real-world entities”*⁴. Other definitions focus on data modelling and reasoning. For example, *“a knowledge graph acquires and integrates information into an ontology and applies a reasoner to derive new knowledge”* [60]. Further, KGs are viewed as *“very large semantic nets that integrate various and heterogeneous information sources to represent knowledge about certain domains of discourse”* [17]. In its essence, KGs are linked data [61]. However, not all KGs are semantic (i.e. KGs that use semantic technology). Non-semantic KGs (also known as property graphs), which do not follow an ontology or a schema exist. This thesis focuses on semantically enriched KGs (i.e. the ones that use an ontology as their schema).
- **Linked Data** - A set of design principles for sharing machine-readable interlinked data on the Web [62]. Details are presented in [61].
- **Linked Data-as-a-Service(LDaaS)**- An architecture that supports

¹<https://www.w3.org/standards/semanticweb/ontology>

²<https://www.ontotext.com>

³<https://www.ontotext.com/knowledgehub/fundamentals/what-is-a-knowledge-graph/>

⁴<https://www.ibm.com/cloud/learn/knowledge-graph>

the reliable and consistent on demand query of Linked Data by online agents [63].

- **Consent Management** - *"A collection of processes that allow or integrate queries upon multiple and autonomous data sources, taking into account data subjects individually given, purpose- and utilizer-specific, and dynamically adjustable consent"* [64]. For example, this is what happens to one's consent during a compliance check and how it is handled by the different processes.
- **Consent Implementation** - A process that includes the semantic representation, visualisation and management of consent's life-cycle (figure 3.1).
- **Consent Life-Cycle** - As shown in figure 3.1, consent can go through various stages. The four main stages can be defined as consent (i) request, (ii) comprehension, (iii) decision and (iv) use. Detailed explanation of each step is presented in [2]. The interaction with consent can begin at any of those stages depending on the situation. The work that this thesis presents focuses mainly on the consent request, comprehension and decision.
- **Compliance based on Informed Consent** - In the scope of this work, compliance is defined as verifying or checking that data is used according to individuals' informed consent. For example, this can be checking if informed consent for GPS data sharing for traffic detection purpose is used for only that purpose. However, the implementation of this functionality is currently out of scope as it focuses primarily on

the GDPR compliant request of consent.

- **Web Ontology Language (OWL)** - OWL is a Semantic Web language for building ontologies by defining classes properties, individuals, and data values in a machine-readable format [65]. The later version of it, called OWL2 ⁵, extends its capabilities by increasing the expressivity power of properties, supporting various datatypes and by having extended annotation capabilities.
- **Resource Description Framework (RDF)** - A World Wide Web Consortium (W3C)⁶ standard for representing metadata in a machine-readable format. Information is modelled in the form of triples (i.e. subject, predicate, object) [66]. An example of a triple is: *Consent hasConsentID ConsentID*, where *Consent* is the subject, the relationship *hasConsent* is the predicate and the object is the *ConsentID*. In 2014, an extension of RDF, called RDF Schema (RDFs) ⁷ was presented. RDFs allows modelling of more complex construct such as classes, data and object properties. More information is provided in [67] and [16].
- **Incentive** - A thing or set of things that can be used to motivate someone to do something⁸. Different types of incentives exist. For example, incentives can be monetary such as extra payments for a service or symbolic such as an impression of saving the environment.
- **Gamification** - A form of incentives, where game elements are used in a non-game environment to increase the participation and motivation

⁵<https://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-overview/>

⁶<https://www.w3.org>

⁷<https://www.w3.org/TR/2014/REC-rdf-schema-20140225/>

⁸<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/incentive>

of individuals [50].

- **Flutter**⁹ - An UI development toolkit developed by Google, which supports the rapid and cross-platform implementation of applications based on the Dart¹⁰ programming language. In comparison to other frameworks, UI development with Flutter is based on reusing, personalising and combining different widgets¹¹ (i.e. a notation that specifies different UI components such as text, colour and containers). Depending on the level of interaction they support, widgets can be stateful or stateless. Stateful widgets support the dynamic change of the UI, while stateless widgets describe the design more precisely.
- **D3.js** - A JavaScript library for data driven visualisations. The library supports dynamic behaviours, different types of graphical visualisations and the use of large datasets. Many visualisation algorithms have been documented and are openly available for reuse. For examples, see the D3.js gallery¹².

2.2 Semantic Models for Consent

This section presents a chronological overview of existing ontologies for consent (following the GDPR [1]). Each subsection provides details about (i) the ontology's purpose, (ii) the language it was build with, (iii) how consent is modelled and (iv) possible applications. The research in [2], which this section is based on, presents a survey paper on this specific topic.

⁹<https://docs.flutter.dev/cookbook>

¹⁰<https://dart.dev>

¹¹<https://docs.flutter.dev/development/ui/widgets-intro>

¹²<https://observablehq.com/@d3/gallery>

2.2.1 Consent and Data Management Model (CDMM)

The Consent and Data Management Model (CDMM)¹³ [68] is an OWL ontology that represents consent and reuses the PROV-O¹⁴ ontology to express provenance information from different systems. Different types of data such as personal, non-personal and even health data are represented as well. Further, CDMM models the format in which consent is requested (e.g. online, app based, audio) and the time of actions. Although, consent is modelled, the ontology presents only a high level model for it. In order for it to be reused for more specific cases such as sensor data sharing in smart cities and for insurance, it needs to be extended with relevant concepts [2]. Despite that, CDMM can still be utilised when modelling generic privacy policies.

2.2.2 GConsent

Pandit et al. [69] present the GConsent¹⁵ OWL ontology, which represents informed consent. GConsent allows modelling and representation of information related to compliance in an extensible and comprehensive manner. The main aim, as stated by Panditt et al. [69], is to model consent as an entity which has various states (e.g. unknown, given, withdrawn) and to allow consent assessment via pre-defined competency questions. Being one of the first ontologies about consent based on GDPR, GConsent is somewhat generic in a sense that it focuses on the overall notion of consent and not on concepts such as its life-cycle, storage or provenance [2]. The ontology can

¹³<https://openscience.adaptcentre.ie/ontologies/consent/docs/index-en.html>

¹⁴<https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

¹⁵<http://openscience.adaptcentre.ie/ontologies/GConsent/docs/ontology>

be either extended to fit UC1 and UC2 or specific concepts can be already reused.

2.2.3 Privacy Ontology (PrOnto)

The OWL-based PrOnto [70] ontology, models GDPR concepts such as privacy agents, data types, types of processing operations and the rights and obligations related to them [2]. PrOnto models both personal and non-personal data and strives to go beyond GDPR. It is generic enough to be utilised in different scenarios when data sharing and compliance are subjects of other laws. However, PrOnto is not an open-access ontology, which complicates its reuse (i.e. specific details about its classes, relationships and axioms are unknown).

2.2.4 Legal Complaint Ontology to Preserve Privacy for the Internet of Things (LloPY)

The Legal Compliant Ontology to Preserve Privacy for the Internet of Things (LloPY) [71] is an ontology that models GDPR concepts, but is not limited to them. In addition to modelling GDPR-compliant consent, the authors in [71] follow the privacy definitions provided in the National Institute of Standards and Technology Interagency report (NIST)¹⁶. The ontology focuses on consent for sensor data. It models consent decisions, retention, disclosure, as well as sensor data by reusing the Semantic Sensor Network ontology (SSN)¹⁷. However, LloPY, like PrOnto, is not an open access on-

¹⁶<https://www.nist.gov/nist-pub-series/nist-interagencyinternal-50report-nistir>

¹⁷<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-ssn/>

tology. As a result, specific objects, their properties, and how they can be reused remains unclear [2].

2.2.5 Business Process Re-engineering and Functional Toolkit for GDPR Compliance (BPR4GDPR)

The Business Process Re-engineering and Functional Toolkit for GDPR Compliance (BPR4GDPR)¹⁸ represents consent as a type of event (e.g. provided, refused, revoked) and GDPR related information that is needed for performing compliance checking. Consent can be modelled to a low level of granularity since BPR4GDPR models specific roles, event types, context types and state types. Details about the ontology are provided in deliverable D3.1¹⁸ of the BPR4GDPR¹⁹ project, but the ontology itself is not publicly available.

2.2.6 SPECIALs Usage Policy Language (SPL)

The SPECIAL's Usage Policy Language (SPL) [31], based on OWL2, is a language for compliance checking and consent modelling which was developed for the SPECIAL-K [31] compliance platform. The vocabulary also models purpose, processing, recipients, temporal duration in a machine-readable format thus can be reused to semantically represent whole privacy policies [2]. However, *"its scope is limited to capturing the permissive nature of given consent in order to compare it with its processing logs to determine (and evaluate) compliance according to the given consent"* [2].

¹⁸<https://www.bpr4gdpr.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/D3.1-Compliance-Ontology-1.0.pdf>

¹⁹<https://www.bpr4gdpr.eu>

2.2.7 Collaborative Privacy Knowledge Management Ontology for the Internet of Things (ColPri)

The ColPri [72] ontology, developed with the OWL and SKOS²⁰, focuses on configuring privacy policies in the Internet of Things (IoT) domain. Consent has two states *given* and *ungiven*. The ontology enables one to represent semantically information disclosures to entities such as third-parties, data controllers, providers, developers, etc. Further, ColPri models personal data as sensitive, for example, criminal and health records related to an individual and can be utilised for modelling privacy policies in the smart cities domain. The difference between ColPri and other ontologies is that it uses both OWL and SKOS, which allows more flexibility of data categorisation [2].

2.2.8 Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV)

The Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV)²¹ [73] models consent and other related concepts such as notice, expiry, and provision from the GDPR as part of privacy policies, which can be used for performing compliance. Furthermore, the ontology has an extended version (also known as DPV-GDPR²²), which models specific knowledge about the legal basis of the GDPR, technical and organizational measures, and processing categories. DPV is open access but its scope is limited as it focuses mainly on the privacy and legal compliance domains.

²⁰<https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/intro>

²¹<https://dpvcg.github.io/dpv/#motivation>

²²<https://dpvcg.github.io/dpv-gdpr/>

2.2.9 Summary

To conclude and based on the literature review in [2], with the available consent ontologies, one can achieve various levels of expressivity when modelling the consent life-cycle. For example, both GConsent¹⁵ and PrOnto [70] are GDPR compliant (i.e. represent consent according to GDPR) and provide temporal information about consent, its purpose, etc., which can be used for provenance. The CDMM¹³ ontology can be modified to comply with GDPR. DPV²¹ focuses on consent as part of privacy policies. ColPri [72] and LloPri [71] can be adapted and used for modelling consent in smart city use cases, while BPR4GDPR can be used for its specific representation of entities involved in the process of consent implementation. Other ontologies that represent consent but do not follow GDPR, which are worth mentioning are the Informed Consent Ontology (ICO)²³(in the medical domain), Onto-Privacy [74] (based on the Italian Personal Data Protection Code²⁴) and the Neurona Ontologies [75] (based on the Spanish National Data Protection²⁵ law). Table 2.1 presents the (open-access) ontologies for consent presented in this section, the main classes related to consent, the consent object properties and the relevant stages from the consent life-cycle that the ontology can model.

²³<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/ico>

²⁴<https://www.garanteprivacy.it/documents/10160/0/Data+Protection+Code.pdf/>

²⁵[https://gdprhub.eu/AEPD_\(Spain\)](https://gdprhub.eu/AEPD_(Spain))

Table 2.1: Overview of Existing Semantic Models for Consent from [2]

Ontology	Classes	Object Properties	Relevant Consent Lifecycle Stage
CDMM	Consent, ConsentFormat, ConsentingParty, ConsentObligation	consent_given_at, consent_given_by, consent_given_for, data_has_format	Request, Comprehension, Decision, Use
GConsent	Consent, Data Subject, Personal Data, Processing, Purpose, Status, Expired, Explicitly Given, Given by Delegation, Implicitly Given, Invalidated, Not Given, Refused, Requested, Unknown, Withdrawn	hasStatus, hasConsent, isActionForPurpose, isContextForConsent, isPersonalDataForConsent, isPreviousConsentFor, isPurposeForConsent, isStatusForConsent, isUpdatedConsentFor, wasProvidedConsent, atLocation, atTime, isProvidedToController	Request, Comprehension, Decision, Use
BPR4GDPR	ConsentProvided, ConsentRevoked, ConsentDenied, DataProcessor, DataSubject, DataController, DataProtectionAuthority, DataProtectionOfficer	isSensitive, isExecutive, isPartOf, contains, isOfState, hasStateValue, hasPotentialStateValue, hasStateType	Request, Decision, Comprehension, Use
SPL and SPLLog	LogEntry, PolicyEntry, ConsentAssertion, ConsentRevocation	spl:hasData, spl:hasProcessing, spl:hasPurpose, spl:hasStorage, spl:hasRecipient, splog:controller, splog:revoke, splog:recipient, prov:atTime, splog:Processor	Request, Decision, Comprehension, Use
DPV	Consent, Purposes, LegalBasis, DataSubject, DataController, Right	hasConsentNotice, hasExpiry, hasExpiryCondition, hasExpiryTime, hasProvisionBy, hasProvisionByJustification, hasProvisionMethod, hasProvisionTime, hasWithdrawalTime, hasWithdrawalByJustification, hasWithdrawalMethod, hasWithdrawalTime, isExplicit	Request, Decision, Comprehension, Use

2.3 Semantic Models for Sensor Data

Sensor technologies are rapidly developing, but the lack of a standard language for describing a sensors definition, attributes and classifications is still a challenge. The following subsections present an overview of the most relevant (to UC1 and UC2) sensor ontologies that are available.

2.3.1 OntoSensor

Russomanno et al. [76] present an approach for constructing a sensor ontology that is a formal conceptualisation of sensors. The presented OntoSensor²⁶ ontology is based on the SensorML²⁷ and the Suggested Upper Merged Ontology (SUMO) [77] and models sensors attributes, performance, capabilities, reliability in a machine-readable format. As smart sensors can also embed computing capabilities, a well-defined and comprehensive sensor ontology should also represent these capabilities (to store, track, search classify data). Although, the ontology is detailed and in theory can be reused for other scenarios, there are inconsistencies in the organisation of concepts and properties which in practise can make its reuse time-consuming as adjustments will be needed.

2.3.2 Sensor Model Language (SensorML)

The SensorML²⁸(version 1.0 and 2.0) language is produced under OGCs Sensor Web Enablement (SWE)²⁹ activity and has been set as a standard for

²⁶<https://mmisw.org/ont/univmemphis/sensor>

²⁷<https://www.ogc.org/standards/sensorml>

²⁸<https://www.ogc.org/standards/sensorml>

²⁹<https://www.ogc.org/node/698>

the semantic representation of sensors. SensorML can be used to represent both sensors and actuators and post-measurement transformation of observations related to them. The language models an XML encoding of different processes related to sensors, their inputs and outputs. It can be used for support for tasking, observation, and alert services, on-demand processing of observations and discovery of sensors.

2.3.3 Ontonym - Sensor

Ontonym-Sensor by Stevenson et al. [78] is a collection of ontologies that represent various pervasive computing concepts such as sensors. The ontology provides a high-level description of sensors and their capabilities (frequency, coverage, accuracy, and precision pairs) in addition to a description of observations (observation-specific information, metadata, sensor, timestamp, and the time period over which the value is valid, the rate of change) [78]. Based on its wide coverage of sensors, Ontonym-Sensor can be applied in various scenarios involving sensors data [78]. However, the ontology is a collection of several separate ontologies thus issues such as duplicates, overlapping object properties and inconsistencies might arise when it is reused.

2.3.4 Semantic Sensor Network Ontology (SSN)

SSN³⁰ describes sensors and their observations and was originally developed for engineers with deep knowledge of sensors [79]. The ontology describes sensors, their observations, the involved procedures, the studied features of interest, the samples used to do so, the features properties being observed

³⁰<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-ssn/>

or sampled, as well as actuators and the activities they trigger. Due to the mainstream use of SSN, a lightweight version of it was released (see [80]) to further ease its usage and application. Nowadays, the SSN ontology is used as a standard W3C³¹ recommendation in the field, however, it does not facilitate reasoning, categorization and abstraction.

2.3.5 Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (SOSA)

The SOSA³² ontology, which is the light-weight version of SSN, is event-centric, which means it focuses on modelling the observations, sampling, actuations and procedures of sensors [81]. While focusing on the interactions between the sensors, being light-weight and easy to understand by a broader audience, the ontology does not provide the needed level of granularity of the sensors' themselves (e.g. specific types of sensors such as GPS, weather, car break sensors). However, SOSA can still be reused for cases where the sensor observations are the main focus.

2.3.6 Summary

Many sensor ontologies exist, however, they focus only on sensors and their observations and do not include concepts such as consent. For smart city sensor data sharing to be GDPR compliant, each consent request needs to inform individuals about the specific source of the data (i.e. the sensor that emits the data). This is a challenging task as only a street in a smart city can have thousands of sensors. Ontologies such as SSN and OntoSensor can be reused (i.e. reuse classes that model different sensors and actuators)

³¹<https://www.w3.org>

³²https://www.w3.org/2015/spatial/wiki/SOSA_Ontology

to extend any existing consent ontology (e.g. GConsent), thus achieving better granularity of details about the consent itself. This will help develop a semantic model for consent that further models types of sensors and their observations.

2.4 Semantic Models for Data Sharing

Data sharing, and more specifically sensor data sharing, is at the core of the processes running in a smart city. Further, as discussed in the introduction of this thesis, data sharing is a complex process between several entities, thus having an ontological representation of it can help achieve transparency and explainability.

The Data Sharing Agreement Privacy Ontology (DSAP) [82] enables medical experts to model the privacy policies of the Data Sharing Agreements (DSAs). Li and Samavi [82] set as their main goal achieving process transparency and accountability when dealing with sensitive data, thus define extensibility to capture dynamic behaviour as a main requirement. The DSAP ontology defines five main concepts, namely, agent (the entity that is responsible for an action), role (expected action of the agent), action (something that is performed by an agent), policy (legal clauses according to DSA) and a dataset (collected private data). One can trace the data sharing process that occurs using the defined concepts and the relationships that exist between them. However, limitations such as the ontology being based only on DSAs and class inconsistencies are present.

Apart from the DSAP ontology, little to no ontologies specifically dedicated to data sharing exists. This can be solved by reusing separate on-

tologies that describe data such as the Data Knowledge vocabulary (DK)³³, the Government Data Vocabulary (GDV)³⁴, the Physical Data Description vocabulary (PHDD)³⁵ with ontologies that describe processes - SKOS²⁰, the Data Reference Model (DRM)³⁶ etc. In addition to this, provenance ontologies such as PROV-O¹⁴ can be reused to achieve full process transparency.

2.5 Semantic Models for Provenance

Lebo et al. [83] define the PROV-O ontology for provenance that allows representing, exchanging and integrating provenance of entities in different systems. Being developed with OWL2, the ontology is lightweight and could easily be mapped to the PROV Data Model, which further introduces concepts about provenance of information from different domains [83]. The starting point of the PROV-O ontology are the concepts of agents, activity and entity. These three classes are further extended with relevant properties and relationships which can be used to achieve a better provenance expressivity. This can be useful for performing GDPR compliance verification, where the time and the activity related to data processing are of significant importance.

A possible application of PROV-O in a provenance use case is presented in [79]. Compton et al. [79] propose combining the PROV-O and SSN ontologies in order to achieve sensor data provenance. Although, the two ontologies are compatible with each other, they are developed from different perspec-

³³<http://www.data-knowledge.org/dk/1.0/index-en.html>

³⁴<http://www.bartoc.org/pl/node/17972>

³⁵<https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/vocabs/phdd>

³⁶<https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/vocabs/drm>

tives. SSN¹⁷ represents sensors and their observations while PROV-O focuses on temporal data, observations, involved entities, etc. However, what both ontologies have in common is the class observation which could be used for their alignment [79]. The alignment of the two ontologies was beneficial, as it provided capabilities for an indepth specification of the sensors observation such as monitoring of state changes and further allowed extra interpretability [79].

2.6 Summary

To summarise, this section presented a literature review or relevant work in the fields of semantic technologies, namely, ontologies for consent, sensors, data sharing and provenance. The presented ontologies for consent, while relevant and informative are somewhat general and developed for a specific purpose, which makes their reuse in different scenarios challenging. Ontologies such as GConsent mainly focus on informed consent, without going into detail about the data and the user, while OntoPrivacy focuses on compliance checking. Despite being useful in their own way, the limitations that all of the reviewed ontologies have in common are: lack user details, the data and the processing applied to it. When it comes to the sensor ontologies, SSN, SOSA and OntoSensor model the sensors needed for UC1 and UC2 thus can be utilised in this thesis. Combining SOSA's ability to describe sensor's observations and SSNs concept of sensors will result in one complete ontology for sensors that has a balance between observations and the sensor. Further as proposed in [79], PROV-O could be utilised so that one could monitor the provenance of information. Finally, the DSAP ontology

can provide useful definitions for data sharing and processing. The main goal of this research is to build one unified semantic model (ontology), which: (i) represents informed consent according to GDPR, (ii) represents sensor data, (iii) includes data sharing processes, (iv) allows provenance monitoring and (v) allows consent to be extended to a contract state.

2.7 Human Behaviour and Consent

Bechmann [35] presents a comparison of how social media platforms (e.g. Facebook³⁷) deal with consent and the applicable laws. One of the main contributions of [35] is the formalisation and proof of the notion of living in "*a blind informed consent culture*" [35]. According to the qualitative study conducted among Danish students in [35], none of the participants had read the privacy policies and had directly consented for their data to be used and shared. Biases are extremely likely to exist because different people are motivated by different things. Being aware of the policies could be a priority of one user but could not be even considered by others simply based on personal preference. By analysing past surveys among EU citizens about social media usage and data privacy rights, Bechmann's [35] work concludes that individuals were showing a greater level of concern regarding their privacy after being subjects to a data misuse. The question of how to motivate users to read and most of all understand the privacy policies arises.

Joergensen [36] conducted a survey amongst Danish students, which aimed to understand their perception of data privacy and consent on social media platforms. The author concludes that individuals are unaware of their pri-

³⁷<https://www.facebook.com>

privacy rights and what happens to their data. The results of the survey in [36] showed that while being somewhat aware of the types of information that is shared, they *"lack knowledge regarding data sharing on a company level and the related privacy risks* [4]. The study proved Bechmann's [35] point that there is lack of awareness of how one's data is shared and dealt with and of the meaning of consent.

When browsing online, people are more concerned with their final goal (getting a result) and are willing to trade privacy for faster results. Of course, people are aware that their every move on the web is recorded but do not take into consideration the various ways their data could be used both for and against them. The work of Ur et al. [84] further confirms that users are uninformed regarding their data usage and the statement that *"it seems people do not understand how cookies work and where data flows"*. Such research leads to the question of how to increase one's awareness of consent and the consequences that might follow [3]. The issue of lack of awareness about consent and GDPR is also present within small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) [85]. The conducted face-to-face interviews with 10 industrial SMEs in [85] showed that employees and companies lack knowledge about GDPR and how to be compliant (e.g. in what cases one needs to request consent from data subjects).

Even when it comes to health, people could still be unaware of what consent means. In particular, an understanding of not only giving consent per se but also understanding of what it implies and of the possible risks is missing. Medical research done in [86] shows that 27 out of 100 did not know which organ will be operated and 44 out of 100 did not know the

exact procedure. Studies showed poor consent form information recall and understanding (USA Medical forms). It could be due to the participation in many trials and thus confusion when asked about specific details. The work of Byrne et al. [86] confirms that while the signed consent form assures the process is legal, it does not guarantee that people understand what consent implies and how their actions could have positive or negative consequences. In the case of medical consent, it can be due to information not clearly defined or patient's mental state. People should have a clear understanding of their privacy rights and how a simple click on the accept button could lead to their data being shared with millions of users and companies. Moreover, one should feel the need to know what consent means and how it affects data privacy. Further discussions on the topic of consent with regards to different privacy concerns of individuals is presented in [87].

A possible way to encourage one's curiosity towards consent is with incentives. *"The main goal of incentives is to change ones mind regarding an action and/or to make one perform an action we want"* [2]. *"In most cases people are willing to share data with institutions, if there is a personal gain such as better service personalisation, financial and health benefits"* [88].

The work of Vassileva in [89], provides an overview of approaches from the behavioural economics and social psychology fields that can be used to increase individuals' interaction with various applications. From economics's perspective, in order to make someone do what you want them to do *"one needs to create an appropriate system of incentives (rewards)"* [89], for example, gamification, which is *"the integration of game mechanics in non-game environments to increase audience engagement, loyalty and fun"* [50].

In gamification, some of the most popular rewards are: status, achievements, quests and ownership. Such example is the incentive mechanism presented in the Comtella [51] platform. For each completed task on the platform, the mechanism rewards users with points. This resulted in a significant but short-term increase of participation [51]. Some users tried to cheat the system by completing as many tasks as possible but with low-quality performance, which led to its overload. In order to solve this issue, reputation as an incentive was introduced in the new version of Comtella. To solve issues such as low user participation, a third incentive in the form of virtual currency (referred to as "c-points") was introduced [89]. The c-point gamification element successfully doubled the tool's ratings, which also helped improve the accuracy of the users' ratings. Platforms such as Comtella, show that there is a need of dynamic incentives which are based on personal behaviour. Motivation could come externally or be found inside every user. According to theories such as the Theory of Cognitive Dissonance³⁸, people compare themselves to others, so an effective and successful incentive should introduce the concept of competition among the users. The rewards must also be visualised so that users can see what they have accomplished. In Comtella, for example, a star symbol with different luminescence levels was used to represent the status of each user [51].

Incentivisation is also used in further other domains, for example, energy efficiency through behavioural change. For example, consider the work in [90] and the Entropy³⁹ project, which aims to create an energy-aware IT ecosystem. Entropy [33] supports energy efficiency in the building sector

³⁸<https://www.slideshare.net/julita01/comtella-adaptive-rewards-mechanism-to-incentivize-participation-in-online-communities>

³⁹<https://entropy-project.eu>

by monitoring users' behavioural changes. Users are presented with specific guidelines and tasks that need to be followed and completed. Users receive discount vouchers as a reward for completing a task. The project showed that with recommended personalized actions to users, a positive change in their behaviour occurs, raising the idea that reducing energy consumption is a part of everyone's responsibility. The average active time of heating or air conditioning systems over a time period of two months decreased close to by half of the initial time [33].

2.8 Consent Visualisation

For machines, semantic models such as ontologies and KGs for consent, provide knowledge in an easily interpretable machine-readable format [4]. However, that is not the case for humans, especially non-experts (i.e. individuals with no knowledge of the Semantic Web). In comparison, there is a variety of Linked Data visualisation tools (e.g. WebVowl⁴⁰, the Knowledge Engineering Assistant (KEATS) [91], VocBench⁴¹) and libraries (e.g. Ontograph⁴², OntoVis [92]) for Semantic Web experts. Laws such as GDPR and specific concepts such as consent are complex to work with for individuals without specialised legal and technical knowledge. At the same time, data processing cannot begin without consent, which should also be informed as defined by GDPR [1] (Art. 7, Rec. 32). Presenting individuals with long texts such as privacy policies, written in a legalese (i.e. legal language) can cause information overload [39]. A way to minimise textual information, while still

⁴⁰<http://vowl.visualdataweb.org/webvowl.html>

⁴¹<http://vocbench.uniroma2.it>

⁴²<https://protegewiki.stanford.edu/wiki/OntoGraf>

preserving its meaning is with the help of visualisations (e.g. graphs, icons, images). For example, a visualisation of Linked Data (e.g. of an ontology) has proven to be useful for humans' comprehension [93] [94] [95]. The value of visualisations is further discussed in [96] and has been one of the main focuses of the Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) [97] field.

However, many challenges regarding the visualisation of KGs such as modular design (e.g. inability to be extended), readability, complexity of the visualisation algorithm and the view itself, still persist as presented in [98]. Having in mind the scope of this thesis, this section presents an overview of research focused only on improving individuals' awareness and comprehension of consent through its graphical visualisation.

2.8.1 Data Track

The Data Track (Fig. 2.1) tool by Angulo et al. [6] focuses on visualising data disclosures with the help of graphs. The tool's primary goal is to increase transparency and raise individuals' awareness of their data sharing. Individuals can personalize their view by selecting a specific icon on the screen and displaying how data is shared. Personal data and its processing are visualised on the UI using a tracing graph. Furthermore, the tool allows users to exercise rights such as changing or removing specific data sharing services. The tool's evaluation revealed that people found the interface and the visualisations on it useful, as both helped them become more aware of what was happening with their data [6].

Figure 2.1: The Data Track Tool by Angulo et al. [6]

2.8.2 The GDPR-compliant and Usable Privacy Dashboard

Similar is the idea behind the privacy dashboard (Fig. 2.2) by Raschke et al. [7]. As shown on Fig. 2.2, the UI's layout comprises of three sections - general functionalities, data overview and general information. By navigating through the dashboard, users can easily view and change their consent decisions, can view specifics about the data sharing they have consented to and all involved entities. What is different in comparison to [6], is that Raske et al. [7] visualise how one's data flows, based on the given consent, with a timeline graph. The tool's evaluation revealed that initially all participants found it difficult to answer questions regarding their data sharing. Even

Figure 2.2: The Privacy Dashboard by Raschke et al. [7]

though the available data filtering options were seen as helpful they were not easily found by the users. Individuals were also confused about the data categorisation (personal, inferred, behavioural, service, incidental and intentional data). Overall, the evaluation showed that the participants were able to use the interface to some extent and get answers to important questions such as: *”Which data did you have to provide when creating an account for this service? Have you disclosed your location voluntarily? Does this service provider track your location?”* [7]. Although limitations regarding its design are present, the privacy dashboard successfully raised user’s awareness about their data sharing rights [7].

2.8.3 The CoRe and CURE UIs

The challenge of consent comprehension by individuals was also explored by Drozd and Kirrane, who proposed the CoRe User Interface (UI) [8] (Fig. 2.3),

and its second iteration called the Consent Request User Interface (CURE) [9] (Fig. 2.4). Both UIs follow GDPR's requirements for requesting consent and similarly to [7] utilise graphical visualisations. In comparison to [6] and [7], Drozd and Kirrane focused on the pre-consent stage of data sharing (i.e. before giving consent). In the CORE UI, graphs are used to visualise possible data flows based on selected consent purposes. Individuals are given the flexibility to personalise their consent by exploring possible consent path on the graph. To avoid issues such as information overload, legal terms were replaced with common "everyday" language.

The evaluation analysis showed that 96% of the users gave consent without understanding the reason for it and its purpose. Regarding the time it took to consent, 48% of the participants declared it took too long to make a decision. When it comes to the UI itself, 67% described it as "too complex" and "time consuming". For 52% it was hard to use. However, the user's feedback of the consent flexibility and graph representation was positive. The graph visualisation of the consent was one of the easiest features to use. The evaluation of the UI confirmed that users focus more on the visual components rather than the information itself.

The second iteration of the UI, called CURE (Fig. 2.4), built for smartphones, allows immediate consent customisation. This is done by providing users with the options to select what specific information to share, for which purposes and with whom [9]. In addition to using, as described, "simple" phrases, the UI provides users with feedback on demand. CURE also provides a step-by-step visualisation of each consent configuration. Actions such as revoking consent are triggered by deselecting options on the UI or by a

Figure 2.3: The CoRe UI by Drozd and Kirrane [8]

sliding motion.

The evaluation showed that the graph visualisation of the data was accepted positively by 92% (total of 35) of the participants, who also noted that color-coding is a useful feature. Similarly, to the evaluation results of the CoRe UI [8], users were pleased with the new way of giving consent and stated four main reasons for that: (1) having a choice, (2) understandable overview of data, (3) having control over their data and (4) usability. The work in [8] and [9] has shown that individuals can benefit from interactive visualisations which support consent customisation.

2.8.4 TransparencyVis

Schufirin et al. [10] further explore the topic of raising awareness regarding data sharing and GDPR by proposing the TransparencyVis (Fig. 2.5) visualisation interface. The main goal of the UI is to visualise data exports

Figure 2.4: The CURE UI by Drozd and Kirrane [9]

from different sources such as Facebook³⁷, Twitter⁴³, Google⁴⁴ and Instagram⁴⁵. The data dumps are visualised with the help of interactive scatter plots, which focus on temporal data changes. Users can import different data zip archives files and view what happened to their data at a specific time via the TimeView page, which supports the exploration of patterns regarding one's data usage. The evaluation of the tool focused on three specific groups of users, namely fundamentalists, pragmatics and unconcerned and aimed to test their comprehension of what is displayed. The analysis showed that after using TransparencyVis, fundamentalists were most willing to change their privacy attitude (how, why and with whom they share personal data) while pragmatics were the least affected. Overall, the tool was deemed useful to individuals who wanted to learn more about what is happening to their personal data. Future work, however, includes improvements of the visu-

⁴³<https://twitter.com/home>

⁴⁴<https://www.google.com>

⁴⁵<https://www.instagram.com>

Figure 2.5: The TransparencyVis UI by Schufrin et al. [10]

alisations (e.g. explore different graph types), visualising data exports in heterogeneous formats and preserving privacy [10].

2.8.5 Summary

Table 2.2 presents an overview of existing solutions and tools for consent visualisation, their main goal and features such as granting and revoking consent, which the tools can support. Further, the table provides information regarding the use of semantic technology and the special features of each tool. Limitations of each study are discussed as well.

Many of the existing tools such as Data Track [6], the CoRe [8] and CURE [9] UIs do not use semantic technology thus do not benefit of its support for data interoperability. Although the Data Track Tool enhances the transparency and traceability of the data sharing process, it was built prior to GDPR and does not implement consent revocation (a vital human right according to GDPR, Art. 17). The CoRe UI, utilises visualisations and

Table 2.2: Overview of Existing Consent Visualisation Tools [4]

Study	Main goal	Can users give consent?	Can users revoke consent?	Does the tool follow GDPRs requirements for informed consent?	Use of semantics?	Special feature	Limitations
Data Track Tool [6]	Enhance transparency regarding data disclosed to online services.	No	No	No	No	Trace view visualisation of user disclosed data.	The tool was built before the acceptance of GDPR. Data sharing preferences (i.e consent) can be modified only if a service allows it. Consent revocation has not been discussed.
CoRe UI [8]	Give users more control of their data sharing and improve their comprehension of consent.	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	A drill-down visualisation of consent information based on specific processes.	67% of the users found the UI prototype complex and the whole process time consuming. 55% defined the consent representation as confusing.
CURE UI [9]	Bring transparency regarding personal data processing and improve the comprehension of consent.	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Visualisation of consent requests based on a purpose with graphs.	Built for laptops and desktops.
Data Flow Visualisation Tool [11]	Raising awareness about consent by visualising what happens to individuals data after consent is given.	No	No	Yes. Only data sharing based on informed consent can be visualised.	Yes. The tool is based on the CampaignNeo Ontology and KG.	Visualisation of data sharing flows.	Consent management features have not been implemented.
CampaNeo UI [4]	Raise the awareness and ease the comprehension of consent with the help of gamification.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes. The tool uses the CampaignNeo ontology and KG.	Consent request in the form of campaigns. Gamification and incentives.	Use of general gamification elements, which while effective do not target all specific user archetypes.

proves that they assist individuals' comprehension of consent request. Its second iteration, the CURE UI, focuses again on the process of requesting consent and utilises graphs. However, the CURE UI was built for laptops and desktops, which restricts its use. Semantics were not used as well. The visualisation tool in [11], although utilising a KG and supporting its visualisation focuses on post-consent data flows and does not support consent management on its own. As part of this thesis, the work in [11] is integrated into the CampaNeo UI, which uses semantics, provides an environment for consent management and raises awareness with the help of gamification. Together, both UIs support the pre- and post-consent comprehension of both machines and humans.

To summarise, as presented in [6] [8] [9] [7] and [10], graphical visualisations can assist individuals' comprehension of consent. Allowing interactivity and personalisation of the presented information makes individuals feel involved and in control of their data. This helps to build trust between data providers and third-party entities and can lead to higher consent rate [35] [36]. However, issues such as information overload can still be present when multiple data processes and entities are involved [6]. One needs to consider the granularity of each visualisation as different individuals have different needs when understanding information.

2.9 Projects Addressing GDPR and Consent

This section presents an overview of completed and ongoing projects that have set as their goals to solve consent and GDPR-related data sharing challenges.

2.9.1 Mining and Reasoning with Legal Texts (MIREL) (January 2016-December 2019)

The MIREL ⁴⁶ project, funded under H2020 by the EU, delivered a framework for representing and interpreting legal data and documents and allowing querying and compliance checking to be done. The projects main goal was not consent representation, however, its major contributions is the PrOnto [70] privacy ontology, which enables one to define legal entities, actions, agents and different types of data: health, ethical, genetic, biometric, sexual, opinion, etc.

2.9.2 Scalable Policy-aware Linked Data Architecture for Privacy, Transparency and Compliance (SPE- CIAL)(January 2017-December 2019)

The SPECIAL⁴⁷ project, funded under the H2020 research and innovation program, addresses the gap between compliance, privacy and Big Data. The main result of the project is the SPECIAL consent, compliance and transparency framework presented in [31] and the SPECIAL SPL language for describing privacy policies (see section 2.2.6). The framework consist of the a consent management component and a transparency and compliance component, which when combined provide the needed means for obtaining, representing and storing user consent and compliance checking. In addition, the project addresses the issue of consent comprehension by presenting the CoRe [8] and CURE [9] UIs that were reviewed in section 2.8.3. The main

⁴⁶<https://www.mirelproject.eu/index.html>

⁴⁷<https://specialprivacy.ercim.eu>

difference between the work done on SPECIAL and in this thesis regarding individual's comprehension is that this research utilises KGs, takes the consent comprehension a step further by presenting individuals with a post-consent data flow visualisation and adopts gamification to raise the consent rates.

2.9.3 Cyber-Physical Social Systems to Support City-wide Infrastructures (CitySPIN) (October 2017-March 2020)

CitySpin ⁴⁸, funded by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency FFG⁴⁹, focuses on ensuring transparency and compliance in smart cities. The project builds upon the findings in SPECIAL and as the main goal to provide a solution that solves the privacy implications of GDPR with the help of semantics. The main contribution of CitySpin is the Cyber-physical Social System (CPSS) [99] vocabulary that represents constraints on data usage within the SPECIAL framework and a workflow for consent modelling. Another development in the project is the CitySpin platform [100] for secure data acquisition and integration across disparate structured, semi-structured and unstructured sources.

⁴⁸<https://projekte.ffg.at/projekt/2764085>

⁴⁹<https://projekte.ffg.at>

2.9.4 Data Governance Framework for Supporting GDPR (DEFEND)(July 2018-March 2021)

DEFEND⁵⁰, an EU H2020 project, focuses on providing a platform GDPR compliance checking to organisations in different sectors by introducing the Model-Driven Privacy Governance paradigm [101], which allows managing privacy models on both planning and operational levels. The main contributions of the project are the ConFls [102] platform that allows organising and performing threat and data analysis and the DEFEND architecture for a platform based on privacy by design principles. Following this, the DEFEND Data Scope Management (DSM) [103] service, which comprises of a set of activities and strategies that can support organisations in demonstrating GDPR compliance, was presented as well.

2.9.5 SOLID (August 2016-ongoing)

The SOLID⁵¹ project presents a platform for decentralised social applications, which supports data interoperability by following Linked Data principles and utilising Semantic Web technologies. SOLID [104] aims to restore individuals' control over their personal data on the Web by providing individuals with a personal online datastore (pod), which can store any type of data and can be hosted on both personal and public servers. Individuals can have multiple pods, which can be requested from different pod providers⁵². By combining several Web standards such as RDF, SPARQL, Linked Data

⁵⁰<https://www.defendproject.eu/horizon-2020/>

⁵¹<https://solidproject.org/about>

⁵²<https://solidproject.org/users/get-a-pod>

Platform ⁵³, SOLID allows data in the pods to be stored in a structured format. In addition, the applications built with the SOLID Protocol [105] do not require authentication as each individual defines the access rights to their pod and data. Currently, there is an ongoing research [106] focused on combining the Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL)⁵⁴ and SPECIAL policies to extend SOLID's authentication mechanisms.

2.9.6 Summary

To conclude, various ways for achieving interoperable, trusted and GDPR compliant data sharing with the help of semantics have been and are still being explored in many projects. Further, there has been a shift towards decentralisation as discussed in [107] and redefining data sharing as shown in SOLID.

⁵³<https://www.w3.org/TR/ldp/>

⁵⁴<https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>

Approach and Methodology

Consent, GDPR and the legal domain have been challenging fields to comprehend due to the many possible interpretations of legal clauses and the complex legal language that is used for both expert and non-expert users. Further, for a machine to be able to comprehend the law (i.e. be contextually aware of different scenarios and the applicable clauses), human knowledge of the domain in a machine-readable format is needed. This chapter presents the approach for answering the main research questions (chapter 1, section 1.3.) and the selected methodology for implementing informed consent with KGs. All thesis results are summarised in appendix C, table C.

3.1 Approach

The main approach to improving the comprehension of consent of machines is with the help of semantics, namely an ontology and a KG. Based on research of existing ontologies for consent and GDPR requirements, five main consent steps (request, comprehension, decision, use and management) can be derived. Together, all these steps form the life-cycle of consent (Fig. 3.1) and are used as a guideline for this work. The **request** step focuses on the request of consent in an informed GDPR compliant manner to individuals.

Figure 3.1: The Life-Cycle of Consent by Kurteva et al. [2]

During the **comprehension** step, the informed consent information is interpreted by individuals. Following this, an informed consent decision (to give or to refuse consent) is made (**decision** step). If consent is refused, at this step, then a new informed consent request can follow. If it is given, a lawful GDPR data processing and sharing can begin (**use** step). However, as each consent has expiration date, the consent metadata needs to be monitored as well. During the **consent management** step the status of consent needs to be checked and updated accordingly. If the status of consent changes to *withdrawn*, *expired*, *invalidated* or *revoked*, a new informed consent request follows. All this information can be represented in a machine-understandable format with an ontology, which supports the interoperability of consent across different organisations and individuals.

When it comes to improving the human comprehension of consent (see the comprehension and decision steps on Fig. 3.1), this work explores techniques from the HCI and Behavioural Science [108] fields to develop a solution that focuses on the comprehension needs of individuals. The selected approach

is inspired by behavioural targeting [109] practices and utilises incentives in the form of gamification that has shown to be an effective approach for increasing user engagement. In this work, gamification mechanisms are presented during the consent request step, before a consent decision is made (pre-consent). The main goals are to (i) increase user interaction through gamification and mitigate blindly given consent and (ii) increase the consent rates. The benefits of it can be noted during the **comprehension** and **decision** steps. However, the individuals' motivation to complete an action or activity (e.g. give consent and participate in a campaign) can be viewed as intrinsic or extrinsic [110]. Intrinsic motivation is *"the direct and personal beneficial effect or reward of a task from a user's point of view"* [4], while extrinsic motivation focuses on the expected outcome after completing a task. A challenge is to implement gamification mechanisms that can cover as many user archetypes (e.g. philanthropist, socialiser, achiever, player) as possible.

To further support the comprehension and decision steps, a visualisation of post-consent (after consent is given) data flow has been developed as well. The main aim of the post-consent visualisations is to provide more transparency into data sharing and to ease the consent comprehension. However, different individuals require different level of detail to comprehend information [111] [112] [113]. While some might understand the presented visualisation with minimum help and text available, others seek more information and focus on the details to better comprehend what is happening to their data. Shneiderman's mantra [114] of presenting users with *"overview first, zoom and filter, then details on demand"*, UI principles such as Gestalt law of grouping [115] and Linked Data visualisation techniques (e.g. using different

visualisation elements such as icons, charts and graphs) as presented in [93] can be used as guidelines for the development of such KG-based consent data flow visualisation. Having this in mind, the developed post-consent visualisation provides both a general overview of campaign-based data sharing and a detailed view for each campaign.

By following systems engineering [116] and requirements engineering [117], GDPR legal requirements for consent were translated into functional and non-functional requirements (see table 3.1). The requirements were used as a guideline for the development and design of the consent solicitation UIs presented in sections 4.2 and 4.4. Table 3.1 presents these requirements and the main stage of the consent decision process that they refer to: pre-, post-consent or both. The evaluation follows a qualitative evaluation approach [118] focused on subjective assessment of human behaviour and cognitive processes such as comprehension related to consent via crowdsourcing [119]. Evaluation details and results are presented in chapter 5.

3.2 Methodology

This section presents an overview of this thesis's methodology (Fig. 3.2). As presented on Fig. 3.2, the methodology consists of four main steps. During step 1, the smashHitCore¹⁰ ontology for secure and trusted data sharing in the smart cities and insurance domains was built. The ontology is a result of the collaborative effort of individuals from various backgrounds (i.e. Semantic Web, privacy and security, law, insurance and mobility) and focuses on the reuse of classes and object properties from existing ontologies for consent, contracts, sensor data, data processing and the involved entities.

Table 3.1: Functional and Non-functional Requirements

Functional Requirements	
Users should be able to give informed consent.	Pre-Consent
Users should be able to revoke consent at any time.	
Users should be informed of what data is collected.	
Users should be informed of the purpose of the consent.	
Users should be informed of the duration of the campaign.	
Users should be informed of the start/end date of a campaign.	
Users should be informed of the type of data processing that will be applied to their data.	
Users should be informed of the identity of the data controller.	
Users should be informed of the identity of the data processor.	
Users should be able to collect points for each data type they share.	
Users should be able to exchange their collected points for rewards.	
Users should be able to see their position on the leaders board.	Post-Consent
Users should be able to view how their data is used post-consent.	
Users should be able to view how data is used in a specific campaign post-consent.	
Users should be able to view which company uses their data at any time post-consent.	
Users should be able to change the colour-scheme of the UI at anytime.	
Users should be able to interact with the graphical visualisation of their data flows.	
Non-Functional Requirements	
The system should be compliant with GDPR's requirements for informed consent.	Pre-Consent
The system should present the only information needed for informed consent.	
The system should present information in an easily understandable manner.	
The system should be able to present users with new campaigns.	
The system should be able to present users with their active campaigns.	
The system should be able to update users' points.	
The system should be able to semantically annotate users' consent decisions.	Post-Consent
The system should be able to connect to the underlying semantic model via APIs.	
The system should be able to query the KG with SPARQL.	
The system should be able to visualise data flows based on SPARQL queries of the KG.	Both
The system should be reliable.	
The system should execute users' actions in a reasonable amount of time (within 5 sec).	
The system should be able to handle all user actions.	
The system should be platform-independent.	

At its core, the methodology used for the ontology engineering follows the methodology in [120] and consists of the following steps:

1. Identification of the main use cases, the range of intended users and specific use-case related requirements (i.e. competency questions) (table 5.1) with industry collaborators.
2. Identification of the main concepts needed for consent and contracts in UC1 and UC2 (chapter 1, section 1.1.1 and 1.1.2). Review of GDPR's requirements for informed consent with legal experts.
3. Gathering and analysis of existing ontologies for consent (see [2]), contracts, sensor data and data processing, which can be reused.
4. Creation of the smashHitCore ontology by reusing specific classes and their properties from existing ontologies. Definition of new use case specific concepts, when needed.
5. Preservation of consistency by following the "isA" relationship between subclasses and classes (e.g. Sensor *isA* Device). Capitalisation of each word when labelling classes (e.g. Data Source) and following the British English language standard.
6. Evaluation of the expressivity of the ontology with the derived competency questions derived during step 1 (table 5.1).
7. Correctness evaluation of the ontology with the HermiT¹ reasoner.
8. Editing and reviewing of the ontology again if needed.

¹<http://www.hermit-reasoner.com>

Figure 3.2: Methodology Overview

Based on the smashHitCore ontology, a UI for consent solicitation was designed and implemented (step 2) by following Nielsen’s Engineering Model [121] and UX laws [122] such as Hick’s law ², Fitts’s law ³, and Jakob’s law [123]. The UI presents users with informed consent forms that follow the ontology and allows them to exercise their GDPR rights. Further, to raise individuals’ awareness and motivation to consent, the UI includes gamification elements such as leader boards and discount vouchers (coupons). Step 3 deals with the semi-automatic annotation of the received informed consent (from the consent forms) and its insertion into the KG. Once an informed consent instance is created in the KG, specific data flows based on it are queried and visualised on the UI (step 4). Table 3.2 presents each implementation step and the corresponding scientific work that was published during this thesis.

²<https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/article/hick-s-law-making-the-choice-easier-for-users>

³<https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/topics/fitts-law>

Table 3.2: Implementation Steps and Relevant Publications

Implementation Step	Relevant Publication
Step 1: Ontology Engineering	smashHit-Core ¹⁰ [2] [12]
Step 2: UI Design and Implementation (Including Gamification)	[4]
Step 3: KG Construction	[12] [124]
Step 4: KG Data Flow Visualisation (Post-Consent)	[40] [3] [11]

Implementation

This section presents the implementation details and the design decisions of this work at each step of its development based on figure 3.2. Further, figure 4.1 presents the system's layers, their functionality and the used technology (i.e. programming languages, development tool kits, libraries, Semantic Web standards and graph databases). The bottom or **core layer** is a KG stored in the GraphDB ¹ graph database, which by following the smashHitCore ontology as its schema can model various domains related to informed consent. The **semantic/ontology layer**, built with OWL and the Vocbench² environment for collaborative ontology engineering, supports data interoperability is also used for providing a unified data model for informed consent. The **visualisation layer** utilises the D3.js³ Javascript library for data visualisation and visualises data flows from the knowledge graph via a UI. The top layer also referred to as the **user interaction layer** provides a UI for consent management (giving, revoking consent) with gamification. The UI is built with the Flutter⁴ UI development toolkit. As the main point of interaction with the presented KG-based system, the **user interaction layer** focuses on the use of gamification to improve the user's comprehension of consent.

¹<https://graphdb.ontotext.com>

²<http://vocbench.uniroma2.it>

³<https://d3js.org>

⁴<https://flutter.dev>

The next sections present the implementation details for each stage.

Figure 4.1: Knowledge Graph-based Consent Visualisation System's Layers

4.1 Step 1: Ontology Engineering

Following the methodology presented in chapter 3.2, this section presents the main classes, subclasses, object and data properties part of the smashHitCore ontology for consent. This section is also based on the analysis in [2] and is part of [5].

At the time of writing this thesis, smashHitCore¹⁰ consists of 1135 axioms, 134 classes, 32 object properties, 23 data properties and reuses 9 ontologies: GConsent [69], DPV [73], FIBO⁵, PROV-O⁶, OntoSensor [76], schema.org⁷, Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT)⁸, CampaNeo⁹ and Languages, Countries,

⁵<https://spec.edmcouncil.org/fibo/ontology>

⁶<https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

⁷<https://schema.org>

⁸<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat/>

⁹<https://github.com/STIIInnsbruck/CampaNeoUI/blob/master/ontology/CampaNeo.owl>

and Codes (LCC) [125]. The smashHitCore ontology is openly available on Gitlab ¹⁰ and has online documentation¹¹. The description of the ontology follows the guidelines for minimum information for the reporting of an ontology (MIRO) [126]. Figure 4.2 presents an overview of the smashHitCore semantic model - the main classes (in blue) and sub-classes (in white).

The following sections describe the classes relevant for this thesis - consent, data processing, agent, role, location and time and the relationships between them.

Figure 4.2: Overview of smashHitCore

¹⁰<https://gitlab.atb-bremen.de/smashhit/semantic-model/-/blob/master/smashHitCore.owl>

¹¹<https://smashhiteu.github.io/smashHitCore/>

4.1.1 Consent

The class *gconsent:Consent*, models informed consent as defined by GDPR (Art 4(11)). Consent is a dynamic entity (i.e. its status and purpose can change overtime) that can have status (*smashHitCore:ConsentStatus*) such as *gconsent:Invalid*, *gconsent:Withdrawn*, *gconsent:Valid*, *smashHitCore:Granted*. Consent provenance information can be modelled with the object properties *smashHitCore:GrantedAtTime*, *smashHitCore:WithdrawnAtTime*, *smashHitCore:atLocation*.

Figure 4.3: Overview of the Class Consent and Relevant Consent Concepts in smashHitCore

To model detailed information about the context in which a consent decision is made, the class *gconsent:Medium*, which describes the medium through which consent was provided (e.g web form, app, paper) was reused. Consent can be associated with a specific purpose - *smashHitCore:forPurpose* object property with range the class *dpu:Purpose* (e.g *dpu:CommercialInterest*, *dpu:Security*, etc.). Consent can be related to specific data and processing activity via the object properties *smashHitCore:isAboutData* and *smashHitCore:forProcessing*. Figure 4.3 is a visual overview class representation.

4.1.2 Data Processing

Consent must be given for a specific type of data processing (GDPR [1], Art. 4(11), Rec. 32). An overview of the class *dpv:Processing* is presented in Figure 4.4. smashHitCore reuses the concept of data processing from DPV [73] and relevant concepts that describe different types of data processing such as *dpv:Adapt*, *dpv:Align*, *dpv:Collect*, *dpv:Record* and *dpv:Use*. smashHitCore models all concepts related to those events directly listed within GDPR (GDPR [1], Art. 4 (2)) and hence the result is similar to the processing¹² model in GConsent. Each data processing event has input (*rdf:hasInputData*) and output (*rdf:hasOutputData*) data from a resource (*dcat:Resource*).

Figure 4.4: Overview of the Class Data Processing in smashHitCore

¹²<http://openscience.adaptcentre.ie/ontologies/GConsent/docs/ontology#Processing>

4.1.3 Agent and Role

The class *prov:Agent* (Fig. 4.5) represents three types of entities (*prov:Person*, *prov:SoftwareAgent*, *prov:Organization*) that are currently involved in UC1 and UC2. Several types of organisations were reused from the FIBO⁵ and CampaNeo⁹ ontologies (e.g. *fibofbcfe-fse:InsuranceCompany*, *campaneo:AutomobileOrganisation*). The role (class *dcat:Role*) of an agent can change over time and an agent can have multiple roles depending on a given context thus as defined by GDPR the following roles are represented: *smashHitCore:DataProvider*, *smashHitCore:DataController*, *smashHitCore:DataSubject*, *smashHitCore:DataProcessor*, *smashHitCore:DataProtectionOfficer*.

Figure 4.5: Overview of the classes Agent and Role from smashHitCore

An agent can be linked to a current or past role by using the *gconsent:hasRole* and *dcat:hadRole* object properties. Further, agents have personal data associated with them, which is represented by the class *dpv:PersonalDataCategory* (see section 4.3). In cases such as GDPR compliance verification when all entities need to be notified if non-compliance has been detected, smashHitCore models a contact point (*dpv>Contact*) of an agent such as *dpv:Email* and *dpv:TelephoneNumber*.

4.1.4 Data Source and Resource

The class *dpv:DataSource* models the source of the data for which consent is needed. The source can be a device such as a sensor (the class *sensor:Sensor* is reused from OntoSensor [76]), which models a wide spectrum of sensor concepts relevant to our UC1 and UC2. GDPR requires consent to be specific and unambiguous thus we have also reused specific types of sensors such as *sensor:GPS*, *sensor:Motion*. Complex sensors such as *smashHitCore:PhotoelectricSensor*, *smashHitCore:Magnetometer*, *smashHitCore:AirPollutionSensor* have been modelled as well.

Further, the concept of a resource (*dcat:Resource*) is represented. A resource is an asset such as a *smashHitCore:PersonalData*, *dcat:Dataset* or *smashHitCore:SensorData*, which has been produced by an agent. For example, in UC1 and UC2, a vehicle sensor data dataset can be both the input and the output of data processing.

4.1.5 Location and Time

To represent the location and time of consent status updates (e.g. when and where consent was requested, granted, revoked), *smashHitCore* reuses the concepts *LCC:Location* and *time:TemporalEntity*. The *LCC:Location* class has the subclass *LCC:GeographicRegion*, which is used to describe the geographic location in which the status of consent changes. The subclass *smashHitCore:StorageLocation* represents the technical storage location defined by a URL. For example, an URL of a server where the data is stored.

The class *time:TemporalEntity*, which is reused from OWL-Time¹³, is a

¹³<https://www.w3.org/TR/owl-time/>

temporal region that represents a time instant (e.g. the expiration date of consent or a contract) or a period of time (e.g. duration of data progressing, consent). *time:TemporalEntity* has two subclasses *time:Interval* and *time:Instant*, which *time:hasBeginning* and *time:hasEnd*.

4.2 Step 2: UI Design and Implementation (Including Gamification)

This section is based on the work presented in [4] also referred to as the CampaNeo UI for consent solicitation. When requesting consent from individuals via any medium (online, paper, vocal), specific requirements apply. Consent must be informed, specific, unambiguous, freely given (Rec. 32) and requested in *"an intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language"* (GDPR [1], Art. 7). However, informed consent by itself is more than just an action (e.g. user selecting the "Accept" button). Information such as (i) the type of data that is requested, (ii) the specific purpose for its request, (iii) the duration of the consent, (iv) the type(s) of data processing that will be applied and (v) the identity of the agents that the data will be shared with needs to be provided prior to making a consent decision [2] [1]. All this information needs to be provided prior to a consent decision is made in an understandable and easily comprehensible manner to comply with GDPR. In addition, individuals should be able to withdraw it with ease at any time.

The UI development comprised of two iterations. The first iteration fo-

cused on wire-framing with Balsamiq¹⁴ (later versions with Figma¹⁵) and front-end implementation with Flutter. The second iteration focused on implementing the back-end of functionalities such as consent revocation, KG update, gamification mechanism and on front-end design improvements.

4.2.1 First Iteration of the CampaNeo Consent Request UI

Figure 4.6: CampaNeo UI (1): Campaign Overview

To ease granting and revoking consent, the main design approach for the consent request forms was for them to be simple and to follow GDPR's privacy by design requirements such as data minimisation (GDPR [1], Art.

¹⁴<https://balsamiq.com>

¹⁵<https://www.figma.com>

5) (e.g. collect and store only the minimum data needed). The design of the consent forms went through several iterations. The first iteration of the CampaNeo UI (see figure 4.6) (available on Github¹⁶) was designed for small screen devices such as tablets and automotive touch screen displays. By following common UI and UX design principles, a symmetric grid layout was selected for the main screen (see figure 4.6) presented to users, due to its simplicity and ability to evenly distribute and structure UI elements. Figure 4.6 presents an overview of all campaigns created by different companies, which require user's consent. Upon selecting a campaign (figure 4.7), the user is presented with specific campaign details (i.e. an informed consent request form), which follows the underlying semantic model and is GDPR compliant.

Figure 4.7: CampaNeo UI (1): Campaign Details

¹⁶<https://github.com/aneliamk/CampaNeoUI>

An elaborate text description of the campaign can also be viewed by clicking on the name of the campaign (formatted in bold). Next, upon agreeing to participate in a campaign by clicking on the "tick", a consent confirmation request is shown (figure 4.8). During this step the user is once again presented with all data that can be shared for that specific campaign. Different campaigns, based on UC1 and UC2, collect different vehicle sensor data and allow different level of user personalisation. Due to this, the UI presents the user with the option to select which specific data to share within a campaign as presented in figure 4.8. Such practices of active user participation have proven to be effective in making users feel involved [127] and can be used to help raise awareness of data sharing and mitigate "blind consent" [35].

Do you agree to share the following data?

GPS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ABS	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tire Pressure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Speed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
EPS	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 4.8: CampaNeo UI (1): Consent Confirmation

Once informed consent is given, users can select to view their active campaigns (figure 4.9), which are shown in a tabular format. The main information of interest displayed here is the campaign start, end date and a status bar that tracks and visualises the campaign progress based on those dates. To comply with GDPR's requirements for consent revocation, the UI presents the option to withdraw consent by revocation next to each campaign. This

allows users to revoke their consent with ease at any time.

Campaign	Start Date	End Date	Status	
 Volkswagen Speed Tracking	10/01/2020	16/02/2020	80.0%	Details Revoke Consent
 Audi Tire pressure monitoring	14/01/2020	18/03/2020	60.0%	Details Revoke Consent
 SKODA User behaviour	30/01/2020	11/02/2020	40.0%	Details Revoke Consent

Figure 4.9: CampaNeo UI (1): Active Campaigns

The first iteration of the UI was used as a proof of concept and was validated with UC1 and UC2. However, improvements regarding the design and the actual implementation (on the back-end) of functionalities such as consent annotation and consent revocation, within the KG, and the planned gamification approach were needed.

4.2.2 Second Iteration of the CampaNeo Consent Request UI

This section is based on the work done in [4] and presents the fully implemented and improved CampaNeo UI¹⁷ for consent solicitation and its functionalities. One of the main differences regarding the UI's design, is the change of the light colour scheme to dark in order to minimise distractions. In cases such as granting consent during the night in a vehicle, bright colours can be distracting [128].

¹⁷<https://stiinnsbruck.github.io/Campaneio-UI/build/web/index.html#/>

Figure 4.10: CampaNeo UI (2): Main Page

By following the initial design ideas (i.e. grid layout) for the main page of the UI as presented in section 4.2.1, figure 4.10 is comprised out of four tiles that act as a navigation to the different functionalities, which the UI provides. To search for new campaigns, users can select the "New Campaigns" tile, which presents them with a grid view of all available campaigns. Consent is requested in an informed way (figure 4.11). All of the campaign information is fetched directly from a GraphQL endpoint, which mirrors the underlying semantic model, and is visualised on the UI where consent can be requested.

By following GDPR's requirement for consent, the users are free to accept or decline a campaign. Similarly to the first iteration, users are presented with the option to select what specific sensor data to share. However, the main difference is the added gamification layer (i.e. point based rewards) during the second UI iteration. The UI's main page reflects all changes in users' consent/campaign decisions. Figure 4.12 presents both the updated active campaigns and the collected points that the users have collected. Finally,

Figure 4.11: CampaNeo UI (2): Campaign Details

users can revoke their consent by viewing their existing active campaigns and selecting the revoke button. Once consent is revoked the campaign is removed from users' active campaign list. A demo of the tool is available online ¹⁸.

4.2.3 Gamification

The CampaNeo UI's gamification is inspired by the work in [89] and [50]. To test if such approach would work for consent, a simple yet proven to be effective gamification mechanism in the form of a point-based reward system was implemented. Different types of sensor data are assigned with different amount of points (figure 4.13). The more data users consent to share, the more points they can collect. Once collected, the points can be exchanged for various discount coupons (vouchers) via the "Shop Page" (figure 4.14).

The second gamification element, which has been implemented on the

¹⁸https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=m_aHF710nDI

Figure 4.12: CampaNeo UI (2): Main Page Active Campaigns

Figure 4.13: CampaNeo UI (2): Data Sharing Gamification Element

CampaNeo UI, is a leaders' board (figure 4.15). The idea behind it stems from research in behavioural theory and social sciences that shows that creating competition between users raises their engagement. A similar approach was undertaken in [89]. Figure 4.15 presents the leaders board, which ranks

Figure 4.14: CampaNeo UI (2): Shop Page

Figure 4.15: CampaNeo UI (2): Leaders' Board

users based on the number of campaigns that they have participated in. The implemented gamification mechanisms addresses the needs of the player, socialiser and philanthropist archetypes. The player is motivated by the competition that the leaders board creates. The socialiser seeks interactions and increased engagement, which the UI provides via the point exchange system

and the leaders board. *"Philanthropists are, in most cases, the easiest type of archetypes to target as they tend to participate without expecting anything in return"* [4]. All these interactions, however, can happen only after consent is granted. The next section focuses on the semantic annotation of the users' informed consent and the creation of the KG, which keeps provenance of all data.

4.3 Step 3: KG Construction

This section provides an overview of the work in [12]. The KG (i.e. the smashHit legal KG and its earlier version the CampaNeo KG) is the main data source for this work and is based on the smashHitCore ontology, which was earlier presented in section 4.1. The KG helps transform consent data into information and that information into knowledge in a machine-readable format with the help of semantics (climbing up the data, information, knowledge, wisdom (DIKW) [129] pyramid of knowledge management). This section presents details about the semi-automatic creation of the KG from structured contents (e.g. consent request forms such as the ones presented in section 4.2).

Figure 4.16 presents how consent data flows from the UIs to the KG. In the case of the CampaNeo UI for consent solicitation (see section 4.2) data from each consent request form is sent via APIs to pre-defined SPARQL queries, which annotate it. This process is represented by steps 1 to step 5. The main data that is collected and then annotated from the UI forms is individual' consent decision (to give or not to give consent), the purpose of the consent, the collected data based on a campaign (e.g. GPS sensor

data), consent's expiration (start and end date), types of data processing that will be applied to the data, data storage and the identity of the data provider, requester and controller. Steps 6 to 9 show the data flow when consent information needs to be queried from the KG for reasons such as compliance verification as described in [12] and for visualisation purposes as discussed later in section 4.4.

Figure 4.16: Data Flow: From UI to KG

4.3.1 Create Consent Instances

The following Node.js¹⁹ code snippet contains a SPARQL query, which is used for semi-automatically annotating informed consent and creating an instance for it in the legal KG²⁰. New data passed through the API endpoints populates the query, which is executed via a SPARQL endpoint provided by GraphDB. For security and privacy purposes, all personally identifiable data has been anonymised with the SHA 256²¹ [130] hash.

¹⁹<https://nodejs.org/en/>

²⁰<https://smashhitactool.sti2.at/sparql>

²¹<https://emn178.github.io/online-tools/sha256.html>

```
const InsertConsentQuery = `
PREFIX : <http://ontologies.atb-bremen.de/smashHitCore#>
INSERT DATA {:${ConsentID} a
    <http://ontologies.atb-bremen.de/smashHitCore#ConsentID>;
    :isProvidedBy :${DataProvider};
    :inMedium :${Medium};
    :forPurpose :${Purpose};
    :requestedBy :${DataRequester};
    :isAboutData :${Data};
    :hasExpiry :${Duration};
    :hasDataController :${DataController};
    :GrantedAtTime :${GrantedAtTime};
    :RevokedAtTime :${RevokedAtTime}.
    :${Purpose} :forDataProcessing :${DataProcessing}.
}`
```

Example of a specific consent instance insert query, such as the ones shown below, and its result is presented in figure 4.17.

```
PREFIX dc: <http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/>
PREFIX : <http://ontologies.atb-bremen.de/smashHitCore#>
PREFIX dpv: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dpv#>
INSERT DATA{
    :5cf187194c989156427141951c47b5b2de53f1b3b8cea2f2e754edc01bf686ef
    a <http://ontologies.atb-bremen.de/smashHitCore#ConsentID>;
        :inMedium :Online;
        dpv:hasPurpose :Analysing\_GPS\_for\_traffic\_detection;
        :isAboutData :GPS;
        :isAboutData :Speed;
        :GrantedAtTime "2021-05-21T09:03:31.859000+00:00";
        :forDataProcessing :Analysis;
        :forDataProcessing :Collection;
        :hasExpiry "2021-05-21T09:03:31.859000+00:00";
        :atCountry :Austria;
        :atCity :Innsbruck;
        :atState :Tyrol;
        :requestedBy :60a55c9dd79bc757698041ea;
        :hasDataController :60a55c53d79bc757698041e9;
        :isProvidedBy :60s1s15c53d79bc757698041e9.
    :GPS a
    <http://ontologies.atb-bremen.de/smashHitCore#SensorDataCategory>;
        :hasSensorDataCategory :CarData.}
```


Figure 4.17: New Consent Instance Insert Query Result

4.3.2 View Consent Instances

To query information about informed consent instances from the KG upon request, the following SPARQL Query can be used. Figure 4.18 presents the results of the query execution on the KG.

```
PREFIX : <http://ontologies.atb-bremen.de/smashHitCore#>
PREFIX dpv: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dpv#>
SELECT ?ConsentID ?DataProvider ?Purpose ?Data ?Duration ?DataRequester
?DataController ?GrantedAtTime ?RevokedAtTime ?Medium ?State ?City ?Country
WHERE {
  ?ConsentID a
  <http://ontologies.atb-bremen.de/smashHitCore#ConsentID>.
  ?ConsentID :isProvidedBy ?DataProvider.
  ?ConsentID :inMedium ?Medium.
```

```

?ConsentID dpv:hasPurpose ?Purpose.
?ConsentID :requestedBy ?DataRequester.
?ConsentID :isAboutData ?Data.
?ConsentID :hasExpiry ?Duration.
?ConsentID :hasDataController ?DataController.
?ConsentID :GrantedAtTime ?GrantedAtTime.
?ConsentID :RevokedAtTime ?RevokedAtTime.
?ConsentID :atCity ?City.
?ConsentID :atCountry ?Country.
?ConsentID :atState ?State.}

```

	ConsentID	DataProvider	Purpose	Data	Duration	DataRequester	DataController	GrantedAtTime	RevokedAtTime	Medium	State	City	Country
1	:kg234562	:64b67b-d310940d256	:Analysing_GPS_for_traffic_detection	:GPS	:10days	:ca65810660	:c1d5d7d98f0	*2020-06-19 10:35:50**xsd:dateTime	*2020-06-19 10:45:50**xsd:dateTime	:Mobile-App123	:Tyrol	:Innsbruck	:Austria
2	:as120098	:64b67b-d310940d256	:Analysing_GPS_for_traffic_detection	:GPS	:2months	:e54ee7e285f	:xyzmsl2sd	*2021-02-31 23:59:59**xsd:dateTime	*2021-03-31 22:00:01**xsd:dateTime	:MyConsent-App1	:Tyrol	:Innsbruck	:Austria
3	:as120098	:64b67b-d310940d256	:Analysing_GPS_for_traffic_detection	:Fuel	:2months	:e54ee7e285f	:xyzmsl2sd	*2021-02-31 23:59:59**xsd:dateTime	*2021-03-31 22:00:01**xsd:dateTime	:MyConsent-App1	:Tyrol	:Innsbruck	:Austria
4	:as120098	:64b67b-d310940d256	:Analysing_GPS_for_traffic_detection	:GPS	:2months	:e54ee7e285f	:64b67b-d310940d256	*2021-02-31 23:59:59**xsd:dateTime	*2021-03-31 22:00:01**xsd:dateTime	:MyConsent-App1	:Tyrol	:Innsbruck	:Austria
5	:as120098	:64b67b-d310940d256	:Analysing_GPS_for_traffic_detection	:Fuel	:2months	:e54ee7e285f	:64b67b-d310940d256	*2021-02-31 23:59:59**xsd:dateTime	*2021-03-31 22:00:01**xsd:dateTime	:MyConsent-App1	:Tyrol	:Innsbruck	:Austria
6	:f0200gh	:54f6d9020bf	:CO2_emission_detection	:Fuel	:1week	:e54ee7e285f	:e54ee7e285f	*2020-06-19 10:35:50**xsd:dateTime	*2020-06-19 10:45:50**xsd:dateTime	:Mobile-App123	:Madrid	:Madrid	:Spain

Figure 4.18: View All Consent Information (Tabular Format)

4.3.3 Revoke Consent

This section presents how right to be forgotten (GDPR [1], Art.17) is implemented. In order to preserve the provenance of consent and the decisions

about it, upon revocation, a new instance of the consent state (e.g. revoked) is inserted with a timestamp in "xsd:DateTimeStamp" format. Next time a compliance check is performed one can refer to the time of granting and revoking consent based on which a compliance decision can be made. Consent revocation is performed with the help of an INSERT DATA query, which specifies the triple pattern that needs to be met. For example, when a data provider decides to revoke their consent, the following query is executed and the KG is updated with the new consent state as shown on figure 4.19.

```
PREFIX : <http://ontologies.atb-bremen.de/smashHitCore#>
```

```
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
```

```
INSERT DATA{:kg234562 :RevokedAtTime "2020-04-30T09:00:00"^^xsd:dateTime.}
```


Figure 4.19: Revoke Consent (Status Update Query Result)

4.4 Step 4: KG Data Flow Visualisation (Post-Consent)

This section is based on the work presented in [11]. The presented work in this section was inspired by [40]. The previous steps (sections) focused on informed consent requests to end-users and on the semi-automatic annotation of the consent decisions in the legal KG. This section presents the visualisation of campaign data flows (from the KG) after consent is given. Campaign information is queried from the KG and is visualised with the help of graphs with the D3.js Javascript library for manipulating documents based on data.

The KG data visualisation process consisted of (i) review of existing linked data visualisation tools and deriving their limitations, (ii) wire-framing of possible designs of the visualisation and (iii) the implementation of the selected design. As presented in the related work (see section 2.8), most of the existing solutions for consent focus primarily on its request and rarely on what happens after it is granted. Using this as a motivation and by following graph visualisation examples in the case of consent for data sharing such as [6] and [7], initial wire-frames were designed (figure 4.20 and 4.21 as presented in [2]).

4.4.1 First Iteration of the KG Data Flow Visualisation

Based on the proposed approach in section 3.1, the first iteration of the UI present individuals with two types of post-consent data flow visualisations: a general (figure 4.20) and a detailed one (figure 4.21).

Figure 4.20: Current Campaign (Overview Visualisation)

Figure 4.21: Current Campaign (Detailed Visualisation)

4.4.2 Second Iteration of the KG Data Flow Visualisation

Based on the initial wire-frames and on the CampaNeo use cases, design improvements were made and a prototype visualisation was implemented with D3.js. The data itself was queried from the CampaNeo KG, which is stored in the GraphDB graph database. Figure 4.22 presents the systems architecture. Upon granting consent via the UI presented in section 4.2, a

SPARQL query is sent to GraphDB (step 2 and 3) via GraphDB’s SPARQL endpoint. The result of the query (step 4) is then sent to the visualisation module (step 5), where all campaign data is passed to a D3.js visualisation algorithm. The resulting visualisation is displayed back to the user (step 6) via a UI, which has been integrated with the consent request UI from section 4.2. As noted in [11], the front-end is decoupled from the back-end thus the graph database (or the KG stored in it) can be replaced with other instances later if necessary as long as the semantic model is followed, which ensures the GDPR compliance of the system. The UI can be tested online²² and its source code available on GitHub²³.

Figure 4.22: KG Visualisation System Architecture [11]

Figure 4.23 presents the implemented KG visualisation prototype. A star layout was selected due to its simplicity and intuitive representation of data flows [11]. As shown on figure 4.23, the users are presented with a visual representation of all campaigns that they have given consent to. During the consent request stage, each consent and campaign has been associated with a specific purpose and data that will be collected. The current UI reflects that by visualising data types collected by each campaign with different coloured

²²<https://stiinnsbruck.github.io/CampaNeoViz/>

²³<https://github.com/STIInnsbruck/CampaNeoViz>

circles. A legend with the colour and data type association is displayed on the left. As the main purpose of the UI is to be used on small devices such as tablet and GPS systems in a car, two colour-schemes are available (bright as shown on figure 4.23 and dark).

Figure 4.23: KG Data Flow Visualisation UI

The initial idea of a two-level visualisation (i.e. low and high-level visualisation of campaign details) was also implemented. In order to view more details about a specific campaign, users can select the name of the campaign. Further, the UI (figure 4.24) provides a detailed view of each company and the data that they used at a specific time.

Figure 4.24: Campaign Data Flow Details

The following SPARQL query was used for fetching campaign data from the KG on the backend.

```
PREFIX : <http://www.semanticweb.org/ontologies/CampaNeo#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdfschema#>
SELECT ?campaign\_name ?data\_type ?retrieval\_time ?institution\_name
WHERE {
    ?campaignnode a :Campaign.
    ?campaignnode :hasConsentBy :user1.
    ?campaignnode rdfs:label ?campaign\_name.
    ?data :wasRetrievedByCampaign ?campaignnode.
    ?data :hasDataType ?data\_type.
    ?data :wasRetrievedAtTime ?retrieval\_time.
    ?data :isRequestedBy ?institution.
    ?institution rdfs:label ?institution\_name.
}
```

The back end implementation of the main²⁴ and the detailed ²⁵ visualisations can be denoted with the following pseudocode.

```
Establish connection to GraphDB
If the connection fails
    Return an error
If the connection is successful
    Query all campaign information for the user
Verify that data has been successfully queried with console.log()
Construct the overlay for detailed information
Constructing nodes array from the data
    Specify the width, height, timespan and the radius of each node
Create a centered node that represents the user
Set up links such that all nodes are connected with the center node
For each campaign
    For each data type that is shared
        Display each data type as a circle
        Assign each data type a specific colour
        Return an updated visualisation
Make each campaign node clickable
For each selected campaign node
    Append specific data
    Create a list with containers for each data type
    Display the shared data type, the time and the associated company
Return the updated visualisation
```

²⁴https://github.com/STIIInnsbruck/CampaNeoViz/blob/main/campaign_network_d3/src/index.ts

²⁵https://github.com/STIIInnsbruck/CampaNeoViz/blob/main/campaign_network_d3/src/detailed_view.ts

4.5 KG for GDPR Compliance

Figure 4.25: Automated GDPR Compliance System Architecture [12]

The work that is briefly discussed in this section is part of [12]. Figure 4.25 presents the architecture of a tool for automated GDPR compliance based on the semantically modelled informed consent KG from section 4.1 and 4.3. The system follows the microservices approach [131] (i.e. all modules are independent and interact through messages) and consists of the following layers: (i) service layer, (ii) security and privacy layer, (iii) scheduler, (iv) serverless layer and (v) remote storage. Each layer has specific functionalities. The **service layer**, which consists of the API and Core sub-layers, supports the consent annotation in the KG, the consent revocation and the automated compliance verification processes. Further, this layer ensures the system's

security by encrypting and when needed decrypting all consent information with a hybrid approach. The **security and privacy layer** focuses on ensuring the confidentiality, integrity and availability of data by utilising the Next Generation Access Control (NGAC) [132] standard and different Policy enforcement Points (PEP), Policy Decision Points (PDP). The **scheduler** supports the scheduling of different events such as automated GDPR compliance verification, while the **serverless layer** assists the scalable query and log of consent and compliance decisions. The **storage layer** consists of the GraphDB graph database, where the legal KG is stored and a NoSQL database, where compliance decisions (and logs) are stored. The specific implementation details of the GDPR compliance tool are presented in [12].

4.6 Summary

To conclude, the sections in this chapter presented design and implementation details for all development steps of this thesis: ontology engineering, consent UI and gamification design and implementation, KG construction, and KG data flow visualisation. Further, they provided an example of the use of the KG for GDPR compliance based on the work in [12]. The next chapter describes the evaluation plan and its execution with regards to the testing of the ontology, the CampaNeo consent UI with gamification and the post-consent KG data flow visualisation.

This chapter presents the evaluation of this thesis’s three main components: the smashHitCore ontology [5], the CampaNeo consent UI [4] with gamification and the post-consent KG data flow visualisation UI [11] from section 3.1). All surveys used for the evaluation and their analysis can also be found in appendices G and H.

5.1 Evaluation of smashHitCore

This section provides details about smashHitCore’s the evaluation set up and results.

5.1.1 Evaluation Set Up

The evaluation of smashhitCore was done with a set of competency questions (table 5.1) (based on GDPR, UC1 and UC2), derived in collaboration with legal and use case experts. The competency questions (table 5.1) for consent are based on GDPR Art. 7, Rec. 32, 42, 43 and are similar to the ones used in [69]. For each competency question, table 5.1 provides a set of relevant concepts that can be used to model the answer. Similarly to [69], smashHitCore was also evaluated with the HermiT reasoner and no inconsistencies

were found.

5.1.2 Results

The evaluation (table 5.1) showed that smashHitCore can model both informed consent and details about specific types of sensors and sensor data. This is not possible when using GConsent¹⁵, CDMM¹³ in a stand-alone way. smashHitCore represents compliance-related information about the different types of agents their contact details and specific types of personal data (e.g., email, username, address), which are not represented in detail in ontologies such as CDMM, GConsent, SPL and SPLog [31]. In comparison to the ontologies in section 2.2, smashHitCore provides a unified and consistent semantic representation of all concepts in one place. The usability and expressivity of smashHitCore were also evaluated through its successful application for compliance verification as presented in [12], for consent management via the developed CampaNeo consent UI [4] (see section 4.2) and for the creation and visualisation of a legal KG based on it (see sections 4.3 and 4.4).

Table 5.1: Evaluation of smashHitCore with Competency Questions [5]

Questions	Relevant smashHitCore concepts and object properties
Informed consent questions:	
What is the purpose of the consent?	<i>gconsent:Consent, dpv:Purpose, dpv:hasPurpose, smashHitCore:hasContext, smashHitCore:atLocation, smashHitCore:inMedium, smashHitCore:isAboutData</i>
What is the duration of the given consent?	<i>smashHitCore:atDateTime, smashHitCore:hasExpirationDate, smashHitCore:DataRetentionDate</i>
What is the status of consent?	<i>gconsent:StatusInvalidFofProcessing, gconsent:Withdrawn, gconsent:StatusValidForProcessing, smashHitCore:Granted gconsent:isStatusFor, gconsent:hasStatus</i>
What is the context of consent?	<i>smashHitCore:Context, smashHitCore:hasContext, smashHitCore:atLocation, smashHitCore:atDateTime, smashHitCore:inMedium</i>
How was consent requested?	<i>gconsent:Medium, consent:ConsentFormat, consent:AppBased, consent:Audio, consent:Video, gconsent:inMedium</i>
How was a consent decision made?	<i>gconsent:Consent, gconsent:Medium, smashHitCore:inMedium, consent:AppBased, consent:Audio, consent:Video</i>
Who provides the consent?	<i>gconsent:Consent, prov:Agent, dcat:Role, smashHitCore:DataSubject, smashHitCore:isProvidedBy</i>
Data source and data processing questions:	
What type of data is consent requested for?	<i>dpv:DataSource, dcat:Resource, smashHitCore:SensorDataCategory, smashHitCore:hasContext, smashHitCore:hasMetadata, smashHitCore:hasAssociation</i>
What processing will be done to the data?	<i>dpv:Processing, dpv:Align, dpv:Erase, dpv:Analyse, dpv:Alter, dpv:Consult, dpv:Record, dpv:Restrict, rdf:hasInputData, rdf:hasOutputData</i>
What is the source of the data?	<i>dpv:DataSource, smashHitCore:Device, sensor:Sensor, smashHitCore:SensorDataCategory, smashHitCore:hasSensorDataCategory</i>
Who is responsible for the data processing?	<i>prov:Agent, prov:Organization, prov:Person, prov:SoftwareAgent, rdf:Role, smashHitCore:DataController, smashHitCore:DataProvider gconsent:hasRole</i>
Agent questions:	
What entities are involved with the data?	<i>prov:Agent, prov:Organization, prov:Person, prov:SoftwareAgent, rdf:Role, smashHitCore:DataController, gconsent:hasRole</i>
Who is the data controller?	<i>rdf:Role, smashHitCore:DataController, gconsent:hasRole</i>
Who is the data subject?	<i>rdf:Role, smashHitCore:DataSubject, gconsent:hasRole</i>
How to identify a person?	<i>dpv:PersonalDataCategory, dpv:Identifying, dpv:Name, dpv:OfficialID, dpv:UID, dpv:Username, dpv:Password, dpv:Contact, smashHitCore:hasContactPoint, dpv:EmailAddress</i>
How to identify an organisation?	<i>dpv:PersonalDataCategory, dpv:Identifying, dpv:Name, dpv:Contact, smashHitCore:hasContactPoint, dpv:EmailAddress</i>

5.2 Evaluation of the CampaNeo Consent Request UI

This section presents the evaluation of the CampaNeo consent request UI and the evaluation results part of [4]. All survey questions are presented in appendix G.

5.2.1 Evaluation Set Up

To evaluate the CampaNeo consent UI and the gamification mechanism, UI and UX testing was done with users based on sample campaigns provided by CampaNeo industry collaborators from the smart city and mobility domains. Due to covid-related regulations during 2020-2022, when the work was done, in-person evaluation was not possible. The evaluation, with an average duration of 25 minutes, took place online via Zoom¹ and Skype². The Think Aloud [133] method was used to monitor how the interactions with the UI and to help note challenges that were encountered by the participants. The participants (21 in total, aged between 18 and 50 years old), which had different educational and professional/industry backgrounds, were invited to participate in the evaluation personally via email, online messaging platforms and via face-to-face interaction. 66.7% of the participants are vehicle owners. 33.3% used their vehicle at least 2-3 times per week.

As presented on Figure 5.1. The evaluation began with an introduction to what campaign, GDPR and consent are, followed by a demographics survey (step 2). To relate participants' answers to specific surveys, while preserving

¹<https://zoom.us>

²<https://www.skype.com>

Figure 5.1: Consent UI and Gamification Evaluation Flow [4]

their anonymity, each participant was asked to generate a unique code³ (used as their ID). To help the participants attune to the UI's purpose, a scenario depicting a real-life sensor data sharing consent request, from the CampaNeo project, was provided. To evaluate the usability of the UI in the given scenario, all participants were asked to complete a set of tasks (Fig. 5.2). For usability comparison purposes, several tasks from the evaluation in [9] were also used (table 5.2). Step 5 focused on evaluation the participants' comprehension of consent and GDPR. Finally, a design survey was used to evaluate the CampaNeo's UI look and the participant's satisfaction with it [4].

5.2.2 Results

Relevant results of the usability, comprehension and design surveys, which helped evaluate if the CampaNeo UI met its goals (raise awareness about consent and GDPR, increase the consent rates and ease giving and revoking consent) are presented in the next sections and in appendices G, sections 1, 2 and 3).

³<https://passwordsgenerator.net/sha1-hash-generator/>

Consent Comprehension

To evaluate if their understanding of consent has changed after using the CampaNeo UI, the participants filled in comprehension surveys (see appendix G, sections 2 and 3) - a combination of multiple-choice and open-answer questions that tested their consent and data sharing knowledge [4]. 100% of the participants were aware of their right to give consent. 85.7% were aware about their right to consent withdraw. 76.2% knew they have a free choice (to consent or not). While 81% were aware of the "right to erasure", more than the half did not know they can access the data they have shared. 76.2% of the participants answered correctly that their data can be used only by the companies having their consent. 61.9% knew that only after consent is given data sharing begins. 81% were able to correctly state the company that requested their consent. More than the half were also able to state other entities involved in their data sharing (28.6% could name several by name, 33.3% said they can recall). Finally, a total of 95.2% knew once consent is withdrawn, data sharing must stop. 47.6% of them noted that it stops when a campaign ends and only 4.8% did not know the correct answer. Positively, the overall answer correctness score (i.e. "*calculated by how many correct answers were selected compared to the amount of actual correct answers*" [4]) of the surveys was greater than 92.86%, which indicates that most participants either gained new (correct) knowledge about consent or improved their current understanding.

The results (see figures 5.3a and 5.3b) show that after using the CampaNeo UI 95.4% knew what consent implies (72.7% agree and 22.7% strongly agree), 86.4% were more aware of the meaning of consent and their GDPR

rights (figure. 5.3b). In addition, 68.2% agree and 31.8% strongly agree that the incentives are attractive and tempting (figure. 5.4). To conclude, the CampaNeo UI raised the consent awareness of its users. The incentives motivated the participants to share data and to consent to campaigns (figure 5.4) - a useful finding for companies in the smart cities, mobility and insurance domains, which depend on data for service provision and optimisation.

Design

Appendix G presents the used design surveys. The CampaNeo UI was described as user-friendly, with regards to the chosen colour pallet, size of the characters on the screen and the organisation of the visual elements on the screen, by more than 95% of the participants [4]. This was also confirmed by the demographics survey, which showed that even non-expert web surfers navigated and used the UI with ease. The UI's design and evaluation was described mostly with positive adjectives as presented on figure 5.5. However, 19% of the participants described the UI as time consuming. This leads to the conclusion that further improvements regarding the speed of giving consent are needed [4].

Usability

As presented in figure 5.2, all of the task have a success rate of over 86.36%. Giving and revoking consent, viewing campaign details, receiving rewards (points) and viewing the remaining points were performed with 100% success rate by all participants. Viewing the rejected campaigns and the incentives, selecting specific data to share with a campaign and exchanging the collected

points were more challenging (average success rate of 92.04%). The evaluation analysis showed that not all participants understood what the word *incentive* means. One possible reason for this can be having participants from diverse educational backgrounds, nationalities and whose native language is not English. For some of the participants, it was not clear from the first use of the UI that they can collect points when sharing their data. This can also indicate that the participants joined the evaluation not because of the promised incentives but based on their curiosity about consent.

Figure 5.2: CampaNeo UI: Success Rate of Tasks [4]

In comparison to the CURE UI, the CampaNeo UI has more added complexity due to the implemented gamification mechanism. Due to this the task completion was not timed as it was in [9] (average of 1 second to perform a task). Instead if a task was completed within a reasonable amount of time it was marked as successful. The results (figure 5.2 and table 5.2) indicate that *"in addition to being able to successfully complete the same tasks (as on the CURE UI), the users of the CampaNeo UI were also able to successfully*

Figure 5.3: Consent and GDPR Comprehension: (a) Evaluation Results of Users' Consent Comprehension and (b) Users' Confidence in Knowledge of GDPR.

Table 5.2: CURE vs CampaNeo Usability Task Comparison [4]

Task	Text of the Task (CURE)	Task	Text of the Task (CampaNeo)
1	Have a look at the detailed overview of the required data processing for the functionality to "display route on map" [9].	1	View a new campaign.
2	Give your consent to process your information to have health data on your device.	2	View details about the new campaign.
3	Give your consent to enable the fitness adviser.	3	Select what data will be shared.
4	Give your consent to turn on the back-up for you data.	4	Give consent.
5	Withdraw your consent to derive your cardio fitness score.	5	Revoke consent for a campaign of choice.

interact with the gamification" [4]. All participants found giving consent to be easy (61.9% of strongly agreed). 42.9% strongly agree that it was easy, 57.1% agreed about the ease of consent revocation (a slight increase in the complexity of the actions). When asked for additional feedback, specific comments included the need for clearly visible "go back" buttons, a possible filtering of the vouchers on the shop page [4]

Gamification

85.7% of the participants felt motivated to share data with CampaNeo. 66.6% stated they might recommend CampaNeo to others. Although the

presented gamification mechanism was limited to specific types of participants, all (31.8% strongly agreed, 68.2% agreed) viewed the incentives as attractive and tempting (figure 5.4 (a)). By creating competition via the leaders' board, the CampaNeo UI raised participants' motivation to share data. However, when using the UI for the first time, not all participants were aware of the point-based gamification mechanisms.

I find the incentives attractive and tempting.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.4: Gamification Results: (a) Overall Incentives' Satisfaction and (b) Motivation to participate in Campaigns (1-Most Disagreeable, 4-Most Agreeable).

Portability.

The initial version of the CampaNeo UI was intended for in-vehicle use on a small device such as a GPS. Other devices, which users viewed as suitable for using CampaNeo on, are smartphones (95.2% agreed) and a tablet (71.4% agreed). This presents a new opportunity for future work where the UI can be adapted for smart phones and consent can be granted on the go.

Figure 5.5: UI Design Survey Feedback

5.3 Evaluation of the Post-Consent KG Visualisation

This section provides details about the evaluation of the post-consent KG data flow visualisation and the evaluation results as part of [11]. All surveys used in the evaluation are presented in appendix H.

5.3.1 Evaluation Set Up

In-person evaluation was not possible due to the covid-related regulations in 2020-2022, when the work was done. To adapt to these settings, online evaluations via Zoom and Skype were performed for a week (appendix H). 25 participants (between 16-50+ years old), were recruited online via online social media platforms and the university network. All participants defined themselves as competent internet users (most spent over 4 hours daily online). A possible indication that they have already encountered various consent request (e.g. cookie banners) online even without realising it [11]. Due to the work's context (vehicle sensor data sharing), data about the participants'

driving experience was collected as well. While 80% have a driving licence, on daily basis, only 40% use their car, 24% use their bicycle, 24% use public transport, 8% use taxi services. The rest 4% stated "flying" as their main means of transport. The evaluation methodology (Figure 5.6) consists of 6 steps. First, by following common UI and UX evaluation practices, the participants were presented with the following scenario:

"Scenario: Congratulations! You finally secured the position you wanted in a big international company. Tomorrow is your first working day and your new boss has organised a special meeting to introduce you to everyone and the current tasks. As most people, you want to be there earlier and make a good first impression. You set up your alarm extra early with the hope to be on time. The day is here and you wake up, get ready and leave for work with your car. Two hours have passed since you left home and you still have not reached your office. The traffic is worse than you have imagined. You have only twenty minutes left before the meeting starts. Suddenly the traffic eases and you are able to reach your destination five minutes before the meeting starts. In the late hours of the day you wonder how the morning and night traffic could be avoided. Suddenly your colleagues inform you that the city council has started a special campaign which aims to solve the traffic situation in the city. You already have installed the required web app and have agreed to share data. Now, after it has been a few days, you are curious about what is happening to your data. You open the app and see the campaigns you participate in" [11].

Next (step 2), the participants were asked to complete a demographics survey (see appendix H, section 1). The comprehension evaluation (step 3)

Figure 5.6: KG Visualisation Evaluation Flow

comprised of two surveys with the same questions, one presented to them before using the UI and one after (see appendix H, sections 2, 4, 5). This helped to compare participants' answers in order to better understand if the post-consent KG data flow visualisation helped improve their comprehension of data sharing and consent. After the initial surveys (step 1-3), the post-consent UI was presented and the participants were given a series of tasks (step 4) with different complexity. The tasks are presented in table F.1. Due to conducting the surveys online and not being able to see the participants' reactions in person, the Think Aloud [133] usability method was utilised. This helped gain a better understanding of how the participants completed the tasks and interacted with the visualisation. Finally, in step 5 and 6, a design survey and the second comprehension survey (step 6) were presented.

5.3.2 Results

The following subsections present the evaluation analysis with regards to the comprehension of consent, the design and usability of the UI and trust for data sharing.

Consent Data Flow Comprehension

The visualisation was able to raise the comprehension of what happens to one's data post-consent of 76.5% of the participants [11]. It also provided a level of transparency that many appreciated. Prior to seeing the visualisation, most participants were sceptical about the company's compliance with GDPR. This changed significantly after using the tool. On the other hand, by providing a transparent view of one's data sharing flows, the UI also raised suspicions in 28% of the participants who initially stated that they trust EU companies with their data.

Design

Design-wise, the UI was viewed as "easy" and "very easy" to use. This was done by utilising a Likert scale (1-very hard, 2-hard, 3-easy and 4-very easy). Most evaluated the design of the UI with 3.4. 96.3% agreed that the visualisation is easily understandable (i.e. the characters on the screen are clearly visible), the rest were neutral. The UI was mostly described as innovative, organised and effective. 2 participants found the visualisation to be complex. However, the overall satisfaction with it was 74.1%.

Usability

Most of the participants completed the given tasks with ease by relying on their intuition. During the evaluation, some participants needed assistance when generating their encrypted ID (used for associating a participant with each survey) and when reloading the UI. Viewing all campaigns and data flows was also not a challenge. However, for some, it was not clear which icons are clickable and which are not at a first glance.

Data Privacy and Trust

60% of the participants believe that their privacy is respected by EU companies, while the rest have doubts. Based on the provided scenario, 48% were willing to share their data with companies as long as there is a personal benefit (e.g. improved services and user experience). Some commented that they have already felt pressured to consent to data sharing in their personal lives. Several participants wished to see even more details about their data sharing and the involved entities (e.g. have a company description available). Without having seen the visualisation UI, only 48% were open to data sharing. The percentage rose to 85.2% after seeing and using the UI (figure 5.7 and 5.8). By providing more transparency into data sharing and making users feel in control of their data, such visualisation tools can raise awareness regarding the possible implications of blindly giving consent. Further, they can help build a stronger sense of trust (of users) in companies, which can lead to increased consent rates.

Would you agree to share vehicle data like GPS location, speedometer data or fuel gauge readings with certain companies?

Figure 5.7: Data Sharing User Evaluation Before using the UI.

Would you agree to share vehicle data like GPS location, speedometer data or fuel gauge readings, if you had the tool available to control the sharing activities?

Figure 5.8: Data Sharing User Evaluation After using the UI.

5.4 Summary

This chapter presented the evaluation of the three main components of this thesis, namely the smashHitCore ontology, the CampaNeo UI with gamification and the post-consent KG data flow visualisation UI. The results, which were presented in the previous sections confirm the hypothesis from chapter 1, section 1.5 and show that the set out goals from section 1.6 have been achieved. To summarise, the following conclusions can be made:

- By utilising the smashHitCore ontology, a legal KG that successfully

supports consent through its whole life-cycle (from the time it is given till its revocation) can be build.

- The developed KG supports data interoperability as it provides machines with a machine-readable and understandable knowledge of consent [12]. These benefits are clearly seen via its application for automated GDPR compliance [12].
- The adopted gamification mechanisms on the CampaNeo UI has improved individuals' comprehension of consent and GDPR and has raised the consent rates [4].
- Post-consent data flow visualisations support individuals in making sense of consent [11].
- Visualisations can help raise awareness of consent and possibly increase the trust between individuals and the companies that consume their data [4] [11].
- There is a demand for consent visualisation tools that focus on both pre- and post-consent explainability [4] [11].

Conclusions and Outlook

Consent is the key to the world of GDPR compliant data sharing, where data has become a highly sought after asset [2]. The smart cities (UC1) and insurance (UC2) use cases, which motivated this work (section 1.1.1 and 1.1.2), have confirmed that there is a need for scalable and sustainable data sharing infrastructures, which support data interoperability across different domains [55]. With the exponential growth of data that is being generated, the concerns of individuals regarding the use of their data and their privacy are rising as well. In addition to focusing on collecting as much data as possible, more companies should consider individuals' needs and the rights. As no data processing can commence prior to receiving informed consent (when it is the primary legal basis), one should aim to achieve a balance when supporting humans and machines in making sense of consent. To avoid GDPR fines, systems' functionality should not be at the cost of data subjects' rights to make informed consent decisions and to withdraw consent at any time [2].

Following the issue of the human and machine comprehension of informed consent and the GDPR, this thesis presented a KG-based approach for the semantic and graphical representation through consent's life-cycle. Based on it, a prototype system, which combines semantics, KG visualisations and

gamification, was developed. The system comprises of (i) the smashHit-Core ontology [5] and a KG [12] for informed consent, (ii) the CampaNeo UI [4] with gamification and (iii) a KG based post-consent data flow visualisation [11]. The components' evaluation has shown that ontologies and KGs can (i) successfully model the dynamic nature of consent through its whole life-cycle, (ii) can support complex tasks such as fully automated GDPR compliance verification [12] and that (iii) KG visualisations can help raise the legal awareness of consent. Further, the evaluation has also shown that incentives, implemented through gamification can help (i) mitigate blindly given consent by increasing the human-computer interactions (i.e. making individuals feel involved and in control of their decisions and data) and (ii) significantly raise the willingness to consent and share data.

6.1 Lessons Learned

The following sections presents the main lessons learned regarding consent for each step of its life-cycle (see section 3.1, figure 3.1) based on [2] [11] [12] [4].

6.1.1 Consent Request

An ontology, which complies with GDPR's requirements for requesting consent, helps establish a common understanding between individuals from different industries of what consent is. Having such ontology, can help request consent in a coherent and GDPR compliant manner [2]. In addition to being beneficial to individuals, an ontology represents the consent in a machine-understandable format thus supporting its interoperability across different

systems as well. Guidelines regarding the semantic representation of consent are presented below.

- **Lesson 1: Consider all applicable laws in the specific domain of data sharing [2].** GDPR protects all EU citizens' data regardless of their location [1] [134]. However, apart from it, each country has its own data protection legislations. For example, in California, the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) [135] applies.
- **Lesson 2: Understand which consent standards already exist.** When dealing with privacy policies and consent, existing recommendations and standards such as the Consent Receipt v1.1 [136] and ISO/IEC 29184:202 [137] can be used as guidelines. Both provide details about the specification of privacy policies and consent records [136].
- **Lesson 3: Follow Semantic Web standards.** As presented in [2], OWL is predominantly used for ontology engineering. For better expressivity and more flexibility when modelling concepts, OWL2, which is a World Wide Web Consortium (W3C)¹ recommendation for ontology engineering, can be used as well. Further, depending on the modelling needs and the purpose of the semantic model RDFs, Knowledge Interchange Format (KIF)², DAML+OIL³, and upper level ontologies such as Dublin Core⁴ can be re-used [2].

¹<https://www.w3.org>

²https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Knowledge_Interchange_Format

³<https://www.w3.org/TR/daml+oil-reference/>

⁴<https://www.dublincore.org>

- **Lesson 4: Model consent-related data and processing.** When building semantic models, represent not only the consent itself as an event (given, revoked) but also the specific data (e.g. sensor data) the consent is given for. This can be done by deriving GDPR and use case-specific competency questions. Having answers to the questions can help understand what level of expressivity the semantic model should provide.
- **Lesson 5: Model consent provenance.** As discussed in [2], it is recommended to model and keep record of both consent granting and refusal. Such information is useful for performing GDPR compliance and auditability [2].
- **Lesson 6: Avoid legalese.** When requesting consent via consent request forms online, for example, present individuals with the minimum information required by GDPR to avoid issued such as information overload. Present all consent information and any additional information in a simple and concise manner.
- **Lesson 7: Collaboration is key when translating law to code.** When building machine-understandable models such as ontologies, it is recommended to involve experts from the legal, industry (use case) and technology domains.

6.1.2 Consent Comprehension

By representing information in a machine-readable format, an ontology supports the consent comprehension of machines. However, humans perceive

visuals such as figures better than text. For this reason, to ease and support the human comprehension of consent, different graphical visualisations can be used. Below are presented some of the lessons learned during this thesis, with regards to easing the comprehension and raising the consent awareness of end-users.

- **Lesson 1: Provide the option to consent customisation.** Both the CoRe [8] CURE [9] UIs allow individuals to select (customise) their consent in terms of selecting its purposes. The CampaNeo UI [4] supports individuals' campaign customisation by providing options for selecting types of data that can be shared.
- **Lesson 2: Use graphs to visualise data flows.** As presented in [8], [9], [6] and [11], graphs are an intuitive visualisation format, which when carefully designed can help individuals better understand data sharing (how data flows) before and after consent is given.
- **Lesson 3: Include the end-user.** This can be achieved through increased interactions with the visualisation (e.g. the UI). Interactive visualisations have shown to make individuals feel in control and can help ease the comprehension of the presented information [40].
- **Lesson 4: Post-consent visualisation of the data flows can increase transparency.** Many individuals know what consent means but are unaware of what happens after consent is given [4]. Using visualisations can help companies to become more transparent in their data sharing practices, which can also help build stronger trust with data providers.

6.1.3 Consent Decision

Individuals' decision to give or not give consent can be influenced by many external and internal factors. Human bias as a result of one's upbringing and cultural differences play a role as well. Through the years, research has shown that consent is blindly given [35]. This contradicts GDPR's requirements for having "truly" informed consent decisions [138]. Based on the developments of the CampaNeo consent request UI (section 4.2), the post-consent KG visualisation UI (section 4.4) and their evaluation results, the following lessons can be derived and used as guidelines to minimise blindly given consent and to raise the consent rates.

- **Lesson 1: Gamification helps to raise consent awareness and the consent rates.** As shown in this thesis, the use of a gamification mechanism can help mitigate blindly given consent by increasing individuals' interaction with the UI, which makes individuals feel involved and in control of their actions (and data). Further, the provided incentives (coupons/vouchers for service cost discounts) have shown to be attractive and to capture individuals' attention when consent is requested. With time, individuals become more aware of which data is requested, and the information provided to them for informed consent as required by GDPR [134].
- **Lesson 2: Different individuals are motivated by different things when it comes to data sharing.** For some individuals, a campaign purpose such as "traffic detection to minimise CO2 emissions" can be enough to make them give consent, while for others a

more personal incentive is needed. Further, *"individuals are more willing to share data if there is a personal benefit and less willing if the action can affect them personally* [88].

- **Lesson 3: Providing more process transparency can lead to increased data sharing** [2] [4]. The work in [11] has shown that individuals are more willing to give consent for data sharing if they have an application that shows what happens to their data post-consent. Currently, even with cookie requests, once consent is granted the cookie disappears. Cookie logs are located deep into the system itself and are not easily accessible by non-expert users. Even if they are retrieved, one needs specialised knowledge of the privacy, security or computer networks domains to interpret the data correctly.

6.1.4 Consent Use

Consent should be used only for the specific purpose it was granted for. Further, it should be possible to revoke it at any time. Here are some of the lessons learned when using one's consent.

- **Lesson 1: Many industry systems cannot always support KG use.** In some cases, there is even a lack of Semantic Web knowledge engineers who can directly use the provided KG. Implementation flexibility is key. Providing APIs, having a standard documentation such as Swagger⁵ and supporting formats such as JSON and JSON-LD can ease the use of a KG.

⁵<https://swagger.io/solutions/api-documentation/>

- **Lesson 2: Follow GDPR Principles.** To ease the compliance process, it is recommended that GDPR principles such as purpose limitation, storage limitation, lawfulness, fairness, transparency and accuracy, integrity, confidentiality and data minimisation are followed (see table 1 in [12]).
- **Lesson 3: Establish privacy and security mechanisms that ensure consent is accessed by only authorised agents.** This can be done by implementing different authorisation mechanisms and encrypting and decrypting information. In [12], we show that a combination of symmetric and asymmetric encryption techniques helps strengthening system's security.

6.1.5 Consent Management

Consent management is a broad topic itself [2] [31] [11] [12]. It can focus specific processes at each consent life-cycle step or on the overall life-cycle. Further in some works, consent management and GDPR compliance based on consent are used interchangeably. As a start, one should establish what consent management refers to in the current system and the processes it covers. Once this is clear the following guidelines can be used.

- **Lesson 1: Consider systems' dependencies.** While receiving informed consent can trigger data processing and sharing to begin, a consent withdraw request will require these processes to be terminated as soon as possible. This can lead to system and process failures due to the need for data but also non-compliance if the data continues to be used. Further, one should consider how to ensure there is no data left

in the system after the execution of the "right to erasure" (GDPR [13], Art. 17), while maintaining the active processes [12].

- **Lesson 2: Ethical considerations.** The ethical concerns regarding consent for data sharing in certain fields, such as health and medical applications are rising. The data's sensitivity level can vary as well. Research has shown that individuals feel more inclined to consent if there is a personal benefit but also feel more cautious of possible data misuse happening [4] [35].
- **Lesson 3: Support auditing.** Providing auditing features is essential for achieving better compliance verification and data sharing transparency [12]. The work in [139] presents different types of transparencies that can be achieved.
- **Lesson 4: Scalability matters.** In industry settings, consent management should be done at scale and processes such as compliance should be performed within seconds. In [12], we have shown that by following a microservices architecture and using KGs, one can build scalable solutions for consent management, which support data interoperability.

6.2 Outlook

The proposed, in this thesis, approach for improving the consent comprehension and the applications built based on it have proven to be effective and usable. However, they are a proof of concept and improvements regarding their implementation will be needed if a deployment in industry settings

is required. The two types of consent visualisation were built separately and although they have been connected on visualisation level, improvements regarding the back-end integration and synchronisation can be made. Registration of users, management of their accounts and providing different levels of access are already planned features for the upcoming developments in smashHit.

A possible future work could be the personalisation of the UIs for each specific user archetypes. Different types of gamifications can be explored as well in order to assess which mechanisms are most effective for data sharing. The modelling of consent can be explored further in other domains apart from smart cities, mobility and insurance and smashHitCore can be extended accordingly. For example, data sharing in the agriculture domain has been gaining popularity within the research community. The smashHitCore ontology can also be extended to cover consent under the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA)⁶ and other data protection laws. As consent is only one of the six GDPR lawful bases for data processing, efforts can be made in modelling the rest. Developments in extending smashHitCore with contracts, their terms and conditions and individuals' obligations have already begun as part of the smashHit project.

⁶<https://oag.ca.gov/privacy/ccpa>

Appendices

Table A.1: GDPR [1] Dictionary of Legal Terms

Term	Definition
GDPR	The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [1], in force since 2018, is a legislation that enforces a stronger data protection regime for organisations that operate in the European Union (EU) and handle EU citizens' data.
Consent	<i>"Any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subjects wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her"</i> (GDPR [1], Art. 4 (11), Rec 32).

Informed Consent	<p><i>"The data subject must at be notified about the controllers identity, what type of data will be processed, how it will be used and the purpose of the processing operations as a safeguard against function creep. The data subject must also be informed about his or her right to withdraw consent anytime. The withdrawal must be as easy as giving consent. Where relevant, the controller also has to inform about the use of the data for automated decision-making, the possible risks of data transfers due to absence of an adequacy decision or other appropriate safeguards"</i> (GDPR [1]).</p>
Data Subject	<p><i>"An identified or identifiable natural person"</i> (GDPR [1], Art. 4(1)).</p>
Data Requester	<p>An individual or an organization that request specific data to be shared. This definition is based on the use cases of both the CampaNeo and smashHit projects.</p>

Data Controller	<p><i>"The natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law" (GDPR [1], Art. 4(7)).</i></p>
Data Processor	<p><i>"A natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller" (GDPR [1], Art. 4(8)).</i></p>
Personal Data	<p><i>"Any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (data subject); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an on-line identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person" (GDPR [1], Art. 4 (1)).</i></p>

Processing	<p><i>”Any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction”</i> (GDPR [1], Art. 4(2)).</p>
Restriction of Processing	<p><i>”The marking of stored personal data with the aim of limiting their processing in the future</i> (GDPR [1], Art. 4(3)).</p>
Pseudonymisation	<p><i>”The processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person”</i> (GDPR [1], Art. 4(5)).</p>

Recipient	<p><i>"A natural or legal person, public authority, agency or another body, to which the personal data are disclosed, whether a third party or not. However, public authorities which may receive personal data in the framework of a particular inquiry in accordance with Union or Member State law shall not be regarded as recipients; the processing of those data by those public authorities shall be in compliance with the applicable data protection rules according to the purposes of the processing"</i> (GDPR [1], Art. 4(9)).</p>
Third Party	<p><i>"A natural or legal person, public authority, agency or body other than the data subject, controller, processor and persons who, under the direct authority of the controller or processor, are authorised to process personal data"</i> (GDPR [1], Art. 4(10)).</p>
Personal Data Breach	<p><i>"A breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed"</i> (GDPR [1], Art. 4(12)).</p>

The right to be forgotten	Data subjects can withdraw their consent at any time. Prior to giving consent, data subjects should be informed of their right to withdraw consent (Art. 17(2)). Consent should be withdrawn with the same ease as when it was given (Art. 7). Further, all entities involved in the consent should be notified of consent status changes (GDPR [1], Art. 19).
Consent Revocation/ Withdraw	When the permission to do something (e.g data sharing) is rescinded or withdrawn.

Abbreviations

Table B.1: Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
ACT	Automatic Contracting Tool
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HCI	Human-Computer Interaction
HTTP	Hyper Text Transfer Protocol
KG	Knowledge Graph
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFs	Resource Description Framework Schema
SHA	Secure Hash Algorithm
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
URI	Unified Resource Identifier
URL	Unified Resource Locator
URN	Unified Resource Name
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
UX	User Experience
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium

Thesis Results

Table C.1: Thesis Results

Resource	Link
smashHitCore ontology	https://gitlab.atb-bremen.de/smashhit/semantic-model
CampaNeo UI with Gamification (Source Code)	https://github.com/STIIInnsbruck/CampaNeoUI
CampaNeo UI with Gamification (Deployed)	https://stiinnsbruck.github.io/Campaneo-UI/build/web/index.html#/
CampaNeo Post-Consent UI (Source Code)	https://github.com/STIIInnsbruck/CampaNeoViz
CampaNeo Post-Consent UI (Deployed)	https://stiinnsbruck.github.io/CampaNeoViz/campaign_network_d3/dist/index.html
CampaNeo ontology	https://github.com/STIIInnsbruck/CampaNeoViz/blob/main/CampaNeoOntology_rdfxml.owl
CampaNeo UI with Gamification Evaluation Results	https://github.com/STIIInnsbruck/CampaNeoUI/tree/master/evaluation
CampaNeo Post-Consent UI Evaluation Results	https://github.com/STIIInnsbruck/CampaNeoViz/tree/main/evaluation

Utilised Technologies

Table D.1: Utilised Technologies

Technology	Link
SPARQL	https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-query/
OWL	https://www.w3.org/TR/owl-ref/
RDF	https://www.w3.org/RDF/
RDFs	https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/
GraphDB	https://www.ontotext.com/products/graphdb/
Swagger	https://swagger.io
Flutter	https://flutter.dev
GraphQL	https://graphql.org
D3.js	https://d3js.org
Vocbench	http://vocbench.uniroma2.it
Protégé	https://protege.stanford.edu

SPARQL Query: Display Consent Instances

Figure E.1 presents the results of querying all KG consent instances and the information related to them in GraphDB. In the figure, the SPARQL SELECT query is displayed on the top of the screen, while the results are in tabular format at the bottom. The instances' information can be used for GDPR compliance based on informed consent as shown in [12].

```

v 1 PREFIX : <http://ontologies.atb-bremen.de/smashHitCore#>
2 PREFIX dpv: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dpv#>
3 SELECT *
4 WHERE {
5   ?ConsentID :isProvidedBy ?Name.
6   ?ConsentID dpv:hasPurpose ?Purpose.
7   ?ConsentID :GrantedATime ?GrantedATime.
8   ?ConsentID :RevokedATime ?RevokedATime.
9   ?ConsentID :isAboutData ?Data.
10  ?ConsentID :hasExpiry ?Duration.
11  ?ConsentID :requestedBy ?DataRequester.
12  ?ConsentID :hasDataController ?DataController.
13 } LIMIT 10
                
```

Run

Showing results from 1 to 10 of 10. Query took 0.1s, moments ago.

ConsentID	Name	Purpose	GrantedATime	RevokedATime	Data	Duration	DataRequester	DataController
1 :44b67b-d310940d256447c6f55a2d3634903detection	:Analysing_GPS_for_traffic_	:Analysing_GPS_for_traffic_	"2020-06-19 10:35:50"^^xsd:date	"2020-06-19 10:45:50"^^xsd:date	:GPS	:10days	:c65810c6d071310abc012899d-1c165d7098f03992f131d-13d21f19c5c58aa767ca3e2a38e0-b8f894e8367830c27ced87e8d4-c63897b4cb1355-9e62c72b4425401	:c65810c6d071310abc012899d-1c165d7098f03992f131d-13d21f19c5c58aa767ca3e2a38e0-b8f894e8367830c27ced87e8d4-c63897b4cb1355-9e62c72b4425401
2 :a8720098	:44b67b-d310940d256447c6f55a2d3634903detection	:Analysing_GPS_for_traffic_	"2021-02-31 23:59:59"^^xsd:date	"2021-03-31 22:00:00"^^xsd:date	:GPS	:2months	:e54ee7e285fbb0275279143ab-c4c554e65374e7b477ecac83a5984	:e54ee7e285fbb0275279143ab-c4c554e65374e7b477ecac83a5984
3 :a8720098	:44b67b-d310940d256447c6f55a2d3634903detection	:Analysing_GPS_for_traffic_	"2021-02-31 23:59:59"^^xsd:date	"2021-03-31 22:00:00"^^xsd:date	:Fuel	:2months	:e54ee7e285fbb0275279143ab-c4c554e65374e7b477ecac83a5984	:e54ee7e285fbb0275279143ab-c4c554e65374e7b477ecac83a5984
4 :a8720098	:44b67b-d310940d256447c6f55a2d3634903detection	:Analysing_GPS_for_traffic_	"2021-02-31 23:59:59"^^xsd:date	"2021-03-31 22:00:00"^^xsd:date	:GPS	:2months	:e54ee7e285fbb0275279143ab-c4c554e65374e7b477ecac83a5984	:e54ee7e285fbb0275279143ab-c4c554e65374e7b477ecac83a5984
5 :a8720098	:44b67b-d310940d256447c6f55a2d3634903detection	:Analysing_GPS_for_traffic_	"2021-02-31 23:59:59"^^xsd:date	"2021-03-31 22:00:00"^^xsd:date	:Fuel	:2months	:e54ee7e285fbb0275279143ab-c4c554e65374e7b477ecac83a5984	:e54ee7e285fbb0275279143ab-c4c554e65374e7b477ecac83a5984
6 :f02009h	:54f49020b9f-b7d7d2b233348cb49f1-b91c72a50e6dc-fa32c7ecab8762e0bbe-f376b154c735ca294b52d923a92	:CO2_emission_detection	"2020-06-19 10:35:50"^^xsd:date	"2020-06-19 10:45:50"^^xsd:date	:Fuel	:1week	:e54ee7e285fbb0275279143ab-c4c554e65374e7b477ecac83a5984	:e54ee7e285fbb0275279143ab-c4c554e65374e7b477ecac83a5984

Table Raw Response Pivot Table Google Chart

Download as

Figure E.1: SPARQL Query: Display Consent Instances

Post-Consent KG Visualisation Evaluation

Tasks

Table F.1 presents a set of tasks that the participants in the evaluation in [11] were asked to complete. Each task was marked as either successful or not successful. Participants' comments, for each task, were recorded as well.

Table F.1: Post-Consent KG Visualisation Evaluation Tasks

Task	Suc- cessful	Not Suc- cessful	Com- ments
Name the campaigns you are participating in.			
List the different types of data that you share.			
Select a specific campaign and view what data is used by the selected campaign.			
List all the companies or institutions that are receiving your data across campaigns.			
Find the campaign which requests the biggest amount of data.			
Find out how often the University of Innsbruck requested your GPS location data.			
Name the campaigns you are participating in.			
List the different types of data that you share.			

CampaNeo Evaluation Survey Results

This section presents the evaluation results derived from the surveys for the CampaNeo UI, which was presented in section 4.2. The analysis was automatically generated by Google Forms¹. The surveys and the anonymised survey results are also available online² in a comma-separated values (CSV) format. For some questions, a Likert scale (1-very hard, 4-very easy) is used.

¹<https://www.google.com/forms/about/>

²<https://github.com/STIIInnsbruck/CampaNeoUI/tree/master/evaluation>

CampaNeo UI Evaluation Survey Results

1. Demographics

What is your age?

21 responses

What is your gender?

21 responses

What is your ethnicity?

21 responses

What is your nationality?

21 responses

What is the highest level of education you have completed/received?

21 responses

What is your current employment status?

21 responses

What is your marital status?

21 responses

Select your level of Internet surfing competency:

21 responses

How many hours a day do you spend on the Internet?

21 responses

What device do you prefer for Internet browsing?

21 responses

Do you own a car?

21 responses

Do you own a driver's license?

21 responses

How often do you drive a car?

21 responses

- Every day
- Two-Three times per week
- Once a week
- Two-Three times per month
- Several times per year
- Not applicable

How often do you drive a car?

21 responses

- Every day
- Two-Three times per week
- Once a week
- Two-Three times per month
- Several times per year
- Not applicable

What is your main mean of transport?

21 responses

- Personal car
- Public transport
- Taxi
- my feet
- Boeing 747
- Bike
- Bicycle

2. User Interface Design Survey

How difficult is reading the characters on the screen?

21 responses

How difficult is differentiating all colour on the screen?

21 responses

What is your opinion about organization of information on the screen?

21 responses

How difficult is it to give consent?

21 responses

How difficult is it to revoke consent?

21 responses

How difficult is it to navigate the application?

21 responses

I can easily give consent.

21 responses

I can easily revoke consent.

21 responses

On a scale of 1 to 4, 1 being the lowest and 4 being the highest, how would you rate the design of the application?

21 responses

I feel motivated to participate in a campaign.

21 responses

I understand what reward I will get for participating in a campaign.

21 responses

I find the incentives attractive and tempting.

21 responses

I would recommend this app to others.

21 responses

If this app is free, I would definitely use it.

21 responses

If the app is not free, I would still use it.

21 responses

I find the colour scheme easy to interpret:

21 responses

Select the adjectives that describe the app the best in your opinion:

21 responses

I can imagine using the app on my mobile device.

21 responses

I can imagine using the app on a tablet.

21 responses

Select your overall satisfaction with the User-Interface:

21 responses

3. Comprehension Survey

What is the GDPR? Select all that apply:

21 responses

Select the correct answers. According to GDPR, I have the right to:

21 responses

What does consent mean to you?

21 responses

What does it mean to give informed consent?

21 responses

- Giving informed consent means that I am aware of what data is share, with whom, for what purpose etc.
- I was asked for consent and I gave my consent.

What you think happens after consent is given.

21 responses

What you think happens after consent is withdrawn.

21 responses

4. Comprehension Survey: Informed Consent

What is a campaign? Select all that apply:

21 responses

Who has access to your data after consent is granted?

21 responses

Can you name all entities that are involved in the data sharing process according to your given consent?

21 responses

Data sharing stops when:

21 responses

I understand what giving consent means.

21 responses

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

I know how to withdraw my consent for a specific campaign.

21 responses

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

I feel more confident in my knowledge of GDPR.

21 responses

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Post-Consent Evaluation Survey Results

This section presents the evaluation results derived from the surveys for the post-consent KG visualisation UI, which was presented in section 4.4. The analysis was automatically generated by Google Forms. The surveys and the anonymised survey results are also available online¹ in a CSV format. For some questions, a Likert scale (1-very hard, 4-very easy) is used.

¹<https://github.com/STIIInnsbruck/CampaNeoViz/tree/main/evaluation>

Post-Consent UI Evaluation Survey Results

1. Demographics

What is your age?

25 responses

What is your gender?

25 responses

What is your ethnicity?

25 responses

What is the highest level of education you have completed/received?

25 responses

What is your marital status?

25 responses

Select your level of Internet surfing competency:

25 responses

How many hours a day do you spend on the Internet?

25 responses

- Less than 1 hour
- 1-2 hours
- 3-6 hours
- More than 6 hours

What device do you prefer for Internet browsing?

25 responses

- Laptop
- Desktop computer
- Tablet
- Smartphone

Do you own a car?

25 responses

- Yes
- No

Do you have a driver's license?

25 responses

- Yes
- No

How often do you drive a car?

25 responses

- Every day
- Several times per week
- Once a week
- No more than a few times per month
- No more than a few times per year
- Not applicable

What is your main mean of transport?

25 responses

- Personal car
- Public transport
- Taxi
- Bicycle
- Boeing 747

2. General Stance on Consent

In a situation like described in the introduction, are you willing to send your user data to companies or institutions, so they can improve user experience more efficiently?

25 responses

If you ever gave your consent to send user data to a company or institution, why did you decide to do so?

25 responses

Would you agree to share vehicle data like GPS location, speedometer data or fuel gauge readings with certain companies or institutions?

25 responses

Do you frequently use social media platforms like Facebook or Instagram?

25 responses

Which, if any, of these messaging apps are you using?

25 responses

Do you think companies and institutions in Europe respect your data privacy?

25 responses

3. CampaNeo User Interface Design

What device did you use to interact with the application?

27 responses

How difficult is reading the characters on the screen?

27 responses

How difficult is differentiating all colours on the screen?

27 responses

What is your opinion about organization of information on the screen?

27 responses

How difficult is it to navigate the application?

27 responses

How would you rate the design of the application?

27 responses

Select the adjectives that describe the application the best in your opinion:

27 responses

Select your overall satisfaction with the user interface:

27 responses

I think the graph is very useful in this visualisation.

27 responses

4. Graph Comprehension Survey: General Knowledge

I understand what is visualised in the application.

27 responses

I can view each campaign easily.

27 responses

I can see who has my data.

27 responses

The graph helped me understand what happens to my data.

27 responses

I feel more confident in my knowledge of data sharing.

27 responses

I understand how to select a campaign.

27 responses

I can easily see what happened to my data at a specific time.

27 responses

5. View on data privacy

Do you think companies and institutions in Europe respect your data privacy?

27 responses

Do you think using this tool creates an added value which was missing before?

27 responses

If such a tool were available to you in any service or application, would you share selected data with a company or institution?

27 responses

Would you agree to share vehicle data like GPS location, speedometer data or fuel gauge readings, if you had the tool available to control the sharing activities?

27 responses

References

- [1] The European Parliament and Council, “General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR),” 2016. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.
- [2] A. Kurteva, T. R. Chhetri, H. J. Pandit, and A. Fensel, “Consent through the lens of semantics: State of the art survey and best practices,” *the Semantic Web journal*, IOS Press, 2021.
- [3] A. Kurteva, “Implementing informed consent with knowledge graphs,” in *The Semantic Web: ESWC 2021 Satellite Events* (R. Verborgh, A. Dimou, A. Hogan, C. d’Amato, I. Tiddi, A. Bröring, S. Mayer, F. Ongenaë, R. Tommasini, and M. Alam, eds.), (Cham), pp. 155–164, Springer International Publishing, 2021.
- [4] S. Rasmusen, M. Penz, S. Widauer, P. Nako, A. Kurteva, A. Roa-Valverde, and A. Fensel, “Raising consent awareness with gamification and knowledge graphs: An automotive use case,” *International Journal on Semantic Web and Information Systems (IJSWIS)*, vol. 18, 2022.
- [5] A. Kurteva, T. R. Chhetri, R. Hilscher, A. Tauqeer, A. Fensel, K. Nagorny, A. Correia, A. Zilverberg, S. Schestakov, T. Funke, and E. Demidova, “The smashHitCore ontology for GDPR-compliant data sharing in smart cities,” *Journal of Web Semantics*, 2022. This manuscript is currently under review.
- [6] J. Angulo, S. Fischer-Hübner, T. Pulls, and E. Wästlund, “Usable transparency with the data track: A tool for visualizing data disclosures,” *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Conference Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2015.

-
- [7] P. Raschke, A. Kpper, O. Drozd, and S. Kirrane, “Designing a GDPR-compliant and usable privacy dashboard,” in *Privacy and Identity*, pp. 221–236, 2018.
- [8] O. Drozd and S. Kirrane, “I agree: Customize your personal data processing with the core user interface,” *Trust, Privacy and Security in Digital Business*, pp. 17–32, 2019.
- [9] O. Drozd and S. Kirrane, “Privacy cure: Consent comprehension made easy,” in *35th International Conference on ICT Systems Security and Privacy Protection*, pp. 1–14, 2020.
- [10] M. Schufirin, S. L. Reynolds, A. Kuijper, and J. Kohlhammer, “A visualization interface to improve the transparency of collected personal data on the internet,” *2020 IEEE Symposium on Visualization for Cyber Security (VizSec)*, pp. 1–10, 2020.
- [11] C. Bless, L. Dtlinger, M. Kaltschmid, M. Reiter, A. Kurteva, A. J. Roa-Valverde, and A. Fensel, “Raising awareness of data sharing consent through knowledge graph visualisation,” in *SEMANTiCS*, 2021.
- [12] T. R. Chhetri, A. Kurteva, R. J. DeLong, R. Hilscher, K. Korte, and A. Fensel, “Data protection by design tool for automated GDPR compliance verification based on semantically modeled informed consent,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 7, p. 2763, 2022.
- [13] Panel for the Future of Science and Technology, “How the General Data Protection Regulation changes the rules for scientific research,” 2019. Available at [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/634447/EPRS_STU\(2019\)634447_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/634447/EPRS_STU(2019)634447_EN.pdf).
- [14] G. Goos, J. Hartmanis, J. V. Leeuwen, D. Hutchison, J. Z. Pan, H. Chen, H. Kim, J.-Z. Li, Z. Wu, I. Horrocks, R. Mizoguchi, and Z. Wu, “The Semantic Web,” in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 2011.
- [15] K. Breitman, M. Casanova, and W. Truszkowski, “Semantic Web: Concepts, technologies and applications,” in *NASA Monographs in Systems and Software Engineering*, 2007.
- [16] G. Antoniou and F. V. Harmelen, “A Semantic Web primer,” MIT Press, 2004.

-
- [17] D. Fensel, U. Simsek, K. Angele, E. Huaman, E. Kärle, O. Panasiuk, I. Toma, J. Umbrich, and A. Wahler, “Knowledge graphs: Methodology, tools and selected use cases,” *Knowledge Graphs*, 2020.
- [18] T. R. Gruber, “A translation approach to portable ontology specifications,” *Knowledge Acquisition*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 199–220, 1993.
- [19] J. Domingue, D. Fensel, and J. Hendler, “Handbook of Semantic Web technologies,” in *Handbook of Semantic Web Technologies*, vol. 1, Springer, 2011.
- [20] L. Aroyo, P. Traverso, F. Ciravegna, P. Cimiano, T. Heath, E. Hyvönen, R. Mizoguchi, E. Oren, M. Sabou, and E. Simperl, “The Semantic Web: Research and applications,” in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 2009.
- [21] H. Jung, H. Yoo, and K. Chung, “Associative context mining for ontology-driven hidden knowledge discovery,” *Cluster Computing*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 2261–2271, 2016.
- [22] S. El-Sappagh, J. M. Alonso, F. Ali, A. Ali, J. Jang, and K. Kwak, “An ontology-based interpretable fuzzy decision support system for diabetes diagnosis,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 37371–37394, 2018.
- [23] S. de Lusignan, S. Shinneman, I. Yonova, J. van Vlymen, A. J. Elliot, F. Bolton, G. E. Smith, and S. O’Brien, “An ontology to improve transparency in case definition and increase case finding of infectious intestinal disease: database study in english general practice,” *JMIR medical informatics*, vol. 5, no. 3, 2017.
- [24] C. König, A. Mengist, C. Gamble, J. Höll, K. Lausdahl, T. Bokhove, E. Brosse, O. Möller, and A. Pop, “Traceability in the model-based design of cyber-physical systems,” *Proceedings of the American Modelica Conference*, 2020.
- [25] M. S. Murtazina and T. Avdeenko, “An ontology-based approach to support for requirements traceability in agile development,” *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 150, pp. 628–635, 2019.
- [26] A. Lakehal, A. Alti, and P. Roose, “A semantic event based framework for complex situations modeling and identification in smart environments,” *International Journal of Advanced Computer Research*, vol. 9, no. 43, pp. 212–221, 2019.

- [27] S. E. Varlan, “Advantages of Semantic Web technologies in the knowledge based society,” *Analele Stiintifice ale Universitatii ”Alexandru Ioan Cuza” din Iasi - Stiinte Economice (1954-2015)*, vol. 2010, pp. 417–422, 7 2010.
- [28] A. Hogan, E. Blomqvist, M. Cochez, C. Damato, G. D. Melo, C. Gutierrez, S. Kirrane, J. E. L. Gayo, R. Navigli, S. Neumaier, A.-C. N. Ngomo, A. Polleres, S. M. Rashid, A. Rula, L. Schmelzeisen, J. Sequeda, S. Staab, and A. Zimmermann, “Knowledge graphs,” *ACM Comput. Surv.*, vol. 54, jul 2021.
- [29] N. Noy, Y. Gao, A. N. Jain, A. Narayanan, A. Patterson, and J. Taylor, “Industry-scale knowledge graphs: Lessons and challenges,” *Queue*, vol. 17, pp. 48 – 75, 2019.
- [30] N. Torzec, “The Yahoo knowledge graph,” 2014. Available at <https://www.slideshare.net/NicolasTorzec/the-yahoo-knowledge-graph>.
- [31] S. Kirrane, J. D. Fernández, P. Bonatti, U. Milosevic, A. Polleres, and R. Wenning, “The Special-K personal data processing transparency and compliance platform,” *arXiv:2001.09461*, 2020.
- [32] J. A. Rojas, M. Aguado, P. Vasilopoulou, I. Velitchkov, D. V. Assche, P. Colpaert, and R. Verborgh, “Leveraging semantic technologies for digital interoperability in the european railway domain,” in *International Semantic Web Conference*, pp. 648–664, Springer, 2021.
- [33] U. Simsek, A. Fensel, A. Zafeiropoulos, E. Fotopoulou, P. Liapis, T. Bouras, F. Terroso-Saenz, and A. Skarmeta, “A semantic approach towards implementing energy efficient lifestyles through behavioural change,” in *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Semantic Systems*, pp. 173–176, 2016.
- [34] T. Heath, J. Domingue, and P. Shabajee, “User interaction and uptake challenges to successfully deploying semantic web technologies,” in *Proceedings of The 3rd International Semantic Web User Interaction Workshop (SWUI2006) and 5th International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC2006)*, 2006.
- [35] A. Bechmann, “Non-informed consent cultures: Privacy policies and app contracts on facebook,” *Journal of Media Business Studies*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 21–38, 2014.

-
- [36] R. F. Joergensen, “The unbearable lightness of user consent,” *Internet Policy Review*, vol. 3, 2014.
- [37] C. Utz, M. Degeling, S. Fahl, F. Schaub, and T. Holz, “(Un)informed consent: Studying GDPR consent notices in the field,” in *Proceedings of the 2019 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, CCS ’19, p. 973990, ACM, 2019.
- [38] J. Korunovska, B. Kamleitner, and S. Spiekermann, “The challenges and impact of privacy policy comprehension,” *Communication & Computational Methods eJournal*, 2020.
- [39] B. M. Gross., “The managing of organizations: The administrative struggle,” *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, vol. 360, no. 1, pp. 197–198, 1965.
- [40] A. Kurteva and H. De Ribaupierre, “Interface to query and visualise definitions from a knowledge base,” in *International Conference on Web Engineering (ICWE)*, pp. 3–10, Springer, Cham, 2021.
- [41] S. Passera and H. Haapio, “Transforming contracts from legal rules to user-centered communication tools: a human-information interaction challenge,” *Communication Design Quarterly Review*, vol. 1, pp. 38–45, 2013.
- [42] S. Passera, “Enhancing contract usability and user experience through visualization - an experimental evaluation,” in *16th International Conference on Information Visualisation*, pp. 376–382, 2012.
- [43] S. Passera, H. Haapio, and M. Curtotti, “Making the meaning of contracts visible - automating contract visualization,” in *Proceedings of the 17th International Legal Informatics Symposium IRIS*, p. 443450, 2014.
- [44] A. Rossi and M. Palmirani, “A visualization approach for adaptive consent in the european data protection framework,” in *2017 Conference for E-Democracy and Open Government (CeDEM)*, pp. 159–170, 2017.
- [45] W. Cleveland and R. McGill, “Graphical perception: Theory, experimentation, and application to the development of graphical methods,” *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, vol. 79, pp. 531–554, 1984.
- [46] W. Edwards, “The theory of decision making,” *Psychological bulletin*, vol. 51, no. 4, p. 380, 1954.

- [47] S. Araiba, “Current diversification of behaviorism,” *Perspectives on Behavior Science*, vol. 43, pp. 157–175, 2020.
- [48] K. Takemura, “Behavioral decision theories that explain decision-making processes,” in *Behavioral Decision Theory*, pp. 143–164, Springer, 2014.
- [49] E. Fehr and A. Falk, “Psychological foundations of incentives,” *European Economic Review*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 687–724, 2002.
- [50] L. Rodrigues, A. Toda, W. Oliveira, P. Palomino, J. Vassileva, and S. Isotani, “Automating gamification personalization: To the user and beyond,” *ArXiv*, vol. abs/2101.05718, 2021.
- [51] H. Bretzke and J. Vassileva, “Motivating cooperation on peer to peer networks,” in *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on User Modeling*, UM’03, (Berlin, Heidelberg), p. 218227, Springer-Verlag, 2003.
- [52] J. Hamari, J. Koivisto, and H. Sarsa, “Does gamification work? – a literature review of empirical studies on gamification,” in *2014 47th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, pp. 3025–3034, 2014.
- [53] K. Seaborn and D. Fels, “Gamification in theory and action: A survey,” *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, vol. 74, pp. 14–31, 2015.
- [54] S. Deterding, D. Dixon, R. Khaled, and L. Nacke, “From game design elements to gamefulness: Defining ”gamification”,” in *Proceedings of the 15th International Academic MindTrek Conference: Envisioning Future Media Environments*, MindTrek ’11, (New York, NY, USA), p. 915, ACM, 2011.
- [55] The smashHit project, “Public report D1.3 public innovation concept.” https://www.smashhit.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/smashHit_D1.3_Public_Innovation_Concept_v100.pdf, March 2021.
- [56] D. Cagánová, A. Stareček, N. Hornakova, and P. Hlásniková, “The analysis of the slovak citizens awareness about the smart city concept,” *Mobile Networks and Applications*, pp. 1–9, 2019.

- [57] X. Ma, Y. Chen, H. Wang, J. Zheng, L. Fu, P. West, J. S. Erickson, and P. Fox, "Data visualization in the Semantic Web," in *Semantic Web Enabled Software Engineering*, 2015.
- [58] P. Lyons, J. S. Wodarski, and M. D. Feit, "Human behavior theory," *Journal of Human Behavior in the Social Environment*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–21, 1998.
- [59] J. Nielsen, "10 usability heuristics for user interface design." Available at <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/ten-usability-heuristics/>.
- [60] L. Ehrlinger and W. Wöß, "Towards a definition of knowledge graphs," in *Joint Proceedings of the Posters and Demos Track of 12th International Conference on Semantic Systems - SEMANTiCS and 1st International Workshop on Semantic Change Evolving Semantics (SuCESS16)*, 2016.
- [61] T. Berners-Lee, "Linked data," *Design Issues*, 2006. Available at <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>.
- [62] C. Bizer, T. Heath, and T. Berners-Lee, "Linked data - the story so far," *International journal on Semantic Web and information systems*, vol. 5, pp. 1–22, 2009.
- [63] L. Rietveld, R. Verborgh, W. Beek, M. Vander Sande, and S. Schlobach, "Linked data-as-a-service: the semantic web redeployed," in *European Semantic Web Conference*, pp. 471–487, Springer, 2015.
- [64] M.-R. Ulbricht and F. Pallas, "Comafeds: Consent management for federated data sources," *IEEE International Conference on Cloud Engineering Workshop (IC2EW)*, pp. 106–111, 2016.
- [65] D. L. McGuinness, F. Van Harmelen, *et al.*, "Owl web ontology language overview," *W3C recommendation*, vol. 10, no. 10, p. 2004, 2004.
- [66] L. Ding and T. Finin, "Characterizing the semantic web on the web," in *The Semantic Web - ISWC 2006* (I. Cruz, S. Decker, D. Allemang, C. Preist, D. Schwabe, P. Mika, M. Uschold, and L. M. Aroyo, eds.), (Berlin, Heidelberg), pp. 242–257, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2006.
- [67] D. Fensel and F. Facca, "Semantic Web: RDF and RDF Schema." Available at <https://www.sti.innsbruck.at/sites/default/files/>

- courses/fileadmin/documents/semweb09-10/03_SW\protect\discretionary{\char\hyphenchar\font}{-}{-}RDF_and_RDFS.pdf, Accessed 12-03-2020.
- [68] K. Fatema, E. Hadziselimovic, H. J. Pandit, C. Debruyne, D. Lewis, and D. O’Sullivan, “Compliance through informed consent: Semantic based consent permission and data management model,” in *PrivOn@ISWC*, 2017.
- [69] H. J. Pandit, C. Debruyne, D. O’Sullivan, and D. Lewis, “GConsent - a consent ontology based on the GDPR,” in *European Semantic Web Conference (ESWC)*, 2019.
- [70] M. Palmirani, M. Martoni, A. Rossi, B. Cesare, and R. Livio, “PrOnto: Privacy ontology for legal compliance,” *Proceedings of the European Conference on e-Government, ECEG*, pp. 142–151, 2018.
- [71] F. Loukil, C. Ghedira, K. Boukadi, and A. Benharkat, “LIoPY: a legal compliant ontology to preserve privacy for the internet of things,” *IEEE 42nd Annual Computer Software and Applications Conference (COMPSAC)*, vol. 02, pp. 701–706, 2018.
- [72] A. Toumia, S. Szoniecky, and I. Saleh, “ColPri: Towards a collaborative privacy knowledge management ontology for the internet of things,” *2020 Fifth International Conference on Fog and Mobile Edge Computing (FMEC)*, pp. 150–157, 2020.
- [73] H. J. Pandit, A. Polleres, B. Bos, R. Brennan, B. Bruegger, F. J. Ekaputra, J. D. Fernández, R. G. Hamed, E. Kiesling, M. Lizar, *et al.*, “Creating a vocabulary for data privacy,” in *OTM Confederated International Conferences” On the Move to Meaningful Internet Systems*”, pp. 714–730, Springer, 2019.
- [74] A. Cappelli, V. B. Lenzi, and R. Sprugnoli, “Modelization of domain concepts extracted from the italian privacy legislation,” in *Workshop on Computational Semantics (IWCS-7)*, 2006.
- [75] N. Casellas, S. Torralba, J.-E. Nieto, A. Merono, A. Roig, M. Reyes, and P. Casanovas, “The Neurona ontology: A data protection compliance ontology,” in *Intelligent Privacy Management Symposium*, pp. 22–24, 2010.

- [76] D. Russomanno, C. Kothari, and O. A. Thomas, "Building a sensor ontology: A practical approach leveraging ISO and OGC models," in *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 2, 2005.
- [77] I. Niles and A. Pease, "Towards a standard upper ontology," in *International conference on Formal Ontology in Information Systems*, vol. 2001, pp. 2–9, 2001.
- [78] G. Stevenson, S. Knox, S. Dobson, and P. Nixon, "Ontonym: a collection of upper ontologies for developing pervasive systems," in *Workshop on Context, Information, and Ontologies at the 6th European Semantic Web conference (ESWC 2009)*, 2009.
- [79] M. Compton, P. Barnaghi, L. Bermudez, R. Garca-Castro, O. Corcho, S. Cox, J. Graybeal, M. Hauswirth, C. Henson, A. Herzog, V. Huang, K. Janowicz, W. D. Kelsey, D. Le Phuoc, L. Lefort, M. Leggieri, H. Neuhaus, A. Nikolov, K. Page, A. Passant, A. Sheth, and K. Taylor, "The SSN ontology of the W3C semantic sensor network incubator group," *Journal of Web Semantics*, vol. 17, pp. 25–32, 2012.
- [80] A. Haller, K. Janowicz, S. Cox, M. Lefrançois, K. Taylor, D. Le-Phuoc, J. Lieberman, R. García-Castro, R. Atkinson, and C. Stadler, "The modular SSN ontology: A joint W3C and OGC standard specifying the semantics of sensors, observations, sampling, and actuation," *Semantic Web*, vol. 10, pp. 9–32, 2019.
- [81] K. Janowicz, A. Haller, S. J. Cox, D. Le Phuoc, and M. Lefrançois, "SOSA: A lightweight ontology for sensors, observations, samples, and actuators," *Journal of Web Semantics*, vol. 56, p. 110, may 2019.
- [82] M. Li and R. Samavi, "DSAP: Data sharing agreement privacy ontology," in *Conference: Semantic Web Applications and Tools for Healthcare and Life Sciences (SWAT4HCLS)*, 2018.
- [83] T. Lebo, S. Sahoo, D. McGuinness, K. Belhajjame, J. Cheney, D. Corsar, D. Garijo, S. Soiland-Reyes, S. Zednik, and J. Zhao, "Prov-o: The prov ontology," 2013. Available at <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>.
- [84] B. Ur, P. G. Leon, L. F. Cranor, R. Shay, and Y. Wang, "Smart, useful, scary, creepy: Perceptions of online behavioral advertising," in *Proceedings of the Eighth Symposium on Usable Privacy and Security, SOUPS '12*, (New York, NY, USA), Association for Computing Machinery, 2012.

- [85] M. da Conceição Freitas and M. Silva, “GDPR compliance in smes: There is much to be done,” *Journal of Information Systems Engineering and Management*, vol. 3, p. 30, 2018.
- [86] D. Byrne, A. Napier, and A. Cuschieri, “How informed is signed consent?,” *British Medical Journal (Clinical research ed.)*, vol. 296, pp. 839 – 840, 1988.
- [87] S. Cao, *Are “informed consents” really informed? A comparison of privacy concerns and behaviours between Chinese and Austrian internet users*. PhD thesis, 07 2021. Available at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353236875_Are_informed_consent_really_informed_A_comparison_of_privacy_concerns_and_behaviours_between_Chinese_and_Austrian_internet_users?channel=doi&linkId=60eeb5fcfb568a7098aa7952&showFulltext=true.
- [88] A. E. Marwick and E. Hargittai, “Nothing to hide, nothing to lose? Incentives and disincentives to sharing information with institutions online,” *Information, Communication & Society*, vol. 22, pp. 1697 – 1713, 2019.
- [89] J. Vassileva, “Motivating participation in social computing applications: a user modeling perspective,” *User Modeling and User-Adapted Interaction*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 177–201, 2012.
- [90] M. Böckle and K. Yeboah-Antwi, “Designing at the intersection of gamification and persuasive technology to incentivize energy-saving,” in *I3E 2019: Digital Transformation for a Sustainable Society in the 21st Century*, vol. 11701, pp. 316–328, 2019.
- [91] M. Eisenstadt, J. Domingue, T. Rajan, and E. Motta, “Visual knowledge engineering,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, vol. 16, no. 10, pp. 1164–1177, 1990.
- [92] W.-C. Lim and C.-S. Lee, “Knowledge discovery through composited visualization, navigation and retrieval,” in *International Conference on Discovery Science*, pp. 377–379, Springer, 2005.
- [93] L. Po, N. Bikakis, F. Desimoni, and G. Papastefanatos, *Linked Data Visualization: Techniques, Tools, and Big Data*, vol. 10. 03 2020.
- [94] M. S. Kahil, A. Bouramoul, and M. Derdour, “Big data and interactive visualization: Overview on challenges, techniques and tools,” in *Advanced Intelligent Systems for Sustainable Development*, 2019.

- [95] E. Yudhanira, “Optimize the user experience of linked data visualization,” 2018. Available at: <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1227892/FULLTEXT02.pdf>.
- [96] Y. Wang, A. Segal, R. Klatzky, D. F. Keefe, P. Isenberg, J. Hurtienne, E. Hornecker, T. Dwyer, and S. Barrass, “An emotional response to the value of visualization,” *IEEE Computer Graphics and Applications*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 8–17, 2019.
- [97] A. Dix, “Human-computer interaction,” in *Encyclopedia of Database Systems*, 2018.
- [98] R. Nararatwong, N. Kertkeidkachorn, and R. Ichise, “Knowledge graph visualization: Challenges, framework, and implementation,” in *2020 IEEE Third International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Knowledge Engineering (AIKE)*, pp. 174–178, 2020.
- [99] J. D. Fernández, M. Sabou, S. Kirrane, E. Kiesling, F. J. Ekaputra, A. Azzam, and R. Wenning, “User consent modeling for ensuring transparency and compliance in smart cities,” *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 465–486, 2020.
- [100] A. Azzam, P. R. Aryan, A. Cecconi, C. Di Ciccio, F. J. Ekaputra, J. D. Fernandez Garcia, S. Karampatakis, E. Kiesling, A. Musil, M. Sabou, *et al.*, “The cityspin platform: A cpss environment for city-wide infrastructures,” *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, 2019.
- [101] C. Feltus, E. Grandry, T. Kupper, and J.-N. Colin, “Model-driven approach for privacy management in business ecosystem,” pp. 392–400, SCITEPRESS - Science and Technology Publications, Lda, 2017.
- [102] D. Alkubaisy., L. Piras., M. Al-Obeidallah., K. Cox., and H. Mouratidis., “Confis: A tool for privacy and security analysis and conflict resolution for supporting GDPR compliance through privacy-by-design,” in *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Evaluation of Novel Approaches to Software Engineering - ENASE*, pp. 80–91, INSTICC, SciTePress, 2021.
- [103] L. Piras, M. G. Al-Obeidallah, M. Pavlidis, H. Mouratidis, A. Tsohou, E. Magkos, A. Praitano, A. Iodice, and B. G.-N. Crespo, “Defend dsm: a data scope management service for model-based privacy by design gdpr compliance,” in *International Conference on Trust and Privacy in Digital Business*, pp. 186–201, Springer, 2020.

- [104] A. V. Sambra, E. Mansour, S. Hawke, M. Zereba, N. Greco, A. Ghanem, D. Zagidulin, A. Abounaga, and T. Berners-Lee, “Solid: a platform for decentralized social applications based on linked data,” *MIT CSAIL & Qatar Computing Research Institute, Tech. Rep.*, 2016.
- [105] W3C Solid Community Group, “The Solid Protocol,” 2019-2021. Available at: <https://solidproject.org/TR/protocol#sotd>.
- [106] L. Debackere, P. Colpaert, R. Taelman, and R. Verborgh, “A policy-oriented architecture for enforcing consent in Solid,” in *WWW2022, the International World Wide Web*, pp. 1–9, 2022.
- [107] R. Verborgh, “Re-decentralizing the Web, for good this time,” in *Linking the World’s Information: A Collection of Essays on the Work of Sir Tim Berners-Lee* (O. Seneviratne and J. Hendler, eds.), ACM, 2022.
- [108] B. Berelson, “Behavioural science,” *Organization Behaviour*, p. 10, 1995.
- [109] J. Jaworska and M. Sydow, “Behavioural targeting in on-line advertising: An empirical study,” in *International conference on web information systems engineering*, pp. 62–76, Springer, 2008.
- [110] G. F. Tondello, R. R. Wehbe, L. Diamond, M. Busch, A. Marczewski, and L. E. Nacke, “The gamification user types hexad scale,” in *Proceedings of the 2016 Annual Symposium on Computer-Human Interaction in Play, CHI PLAY ’16*, (New York, NY, USA), pp. 229–243, ACM, 2016.
- [111] N. Sadeghi, Z. M. Kasim, B. H. Tan, and F. S. Abdullah, “Learning styles, personality types and reading comprehension performance,” *English Language Teaching*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 116–123, 2012.
- [112] S. E. Carlson, B. Seipel, and K. McMaster, “Development of a new reading comprehension assessment: Identifying comprehension differences among readers,” *Learning and Individual Differences*, vol. 32, pp. 40–53, 2014.
- [113] W. Kintsch and E. Kintsch, “Comprehension,” in *Children’s reading comprehension and assessment*, pp. 89–110, Routledge, 2005.
- [114] B. Shneiderman, “The eyes have it: A task by data type taxonomy for information visualizations,” in *The craft of information visualization*, pp. 364–371, Elsevier, 2003.

- [115] L. Graham, “Gestalt theory in interactive media design,” *Journal of Humanities & Social Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 1, 2008.
- [116] K. J. Schlager, “Systems engineering-key to modern development,” *IRE Transactions on Engineering Management*, vol. EM-3, no. 3, pp. 64–66, 1956.
- [117] B. Nuseibeh and S. Easterbrook, “Requirements engineering: A roadmap,” in *Proceedings of the Conference on The Future of Software Engineering, ICSE '00*, (New York, NY, USA), p. 3546, Association for Computing Machinery, 2000.
- [118] J. W. Creswell and J. D. Creswell, “Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches,” Sage publications, 2017.
- [119] D. C. Brabham, *Crowdsourcing*. MIT Press, 2013.
- [120] N. Noy, “Ontology development 101: A guide to creating your first ontology,” in *Technical report KSL-01-05 and SMI-2001-0880*, Stanford Knowledge Systems Laboratory and Stanford Medical Informatics, 2001.
- [121] J. Nielsen, “The usability engineering life cycle,” *Computer*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 12–22, 1992.
- [122] J. Yablonski, *Laws of UX: Using Psychology to Design Better Products & Services*. O’Reilly Media, 2020.
- [123] J. Nielsen, “End of web design,” 2000. Available at <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/end-of-web-design/>.
- [124] A. Breitfuss, K. Errou, A. Kurteva, and A. Fensel, “Representing emotions with knowledge graphs for movie recommendations,” *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 125, pp. 715–725, 2021.
- [125] Object Management Group, “Languages, countries, and codes (LCC) Version 1.1 beta 2.” Available at <https://www.omg.org/spec/LCC/1.1/Beta1/PDF>.
- [126] N. Matentzoglou, J. Malone, C. Mungall, and R. Stevens, “MIRO: guidelines for minimum information for the reporting of an ontology,” *Journal of biomedical semantics*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1–13, 2018.
- [127] S. Kujala, “User involvement: A review of the benefits and challenges,” *Behaviour & IT*, vol. 22, pp. 1–16, 01 2003.

- [128] G. Chen, A. Verner, and D. Arnvist, “A design science study on methods of feedback for in-car gesture-controlled infotainment systems,” 2019. Available at <http://hdl.handle.net/2077/62446>.
- [129] M. Frické, “The knowledge pyramid: a critique of the dikw hierarchy,” *Journal of information science*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 131–142, 2009.
- [130] H. Gilbert and H. Handschuh, “Security analysis of SHA-256 and sisters,” in *International workshop on selected areas in cryptography*, pp. 175–193, Springer, 2003.
- [131] N. Dragoni, S. Giallorenzo, A. L. Lafuente, M. Mazzara, F. Montesi, R. Mustafin, and L. Safina, “Microservices: yesterday, today, and tomorrow,” *Present and ulterior software engineering*, pp. 195–216, 2017.
- [132] International Committee for Information Technology Standards, Cyber security technical committee 1, “American national standard for information technology—next generation access control (NGAC),” 4 2020. (Available at https://standards.incits.org/apps/group_public/project/details.php?project_id=2328).
- [133] J. Nielsen, “Thinking aloud: The 1 usability tool,” 2012. Available at: <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/thinking-aloud-the-1-usability-tool/>.
- [134] The European Union, “Data protection under GDPR,” 2022. Available at: https://europa.eu/youreurope/business/dealing-with-customers/data-protection/data-protection-gdpr/index_en.html.
- [135] California Legislative Information, “California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA),” 2018. Available at: https://leginfo.ca.gov/faces/codes_displayText.xhtml?division=3.&part=4.&lawCode=CIV&title=1.81.5.
- [136] Consent & Information Sharing Work Group, “Consent receipt specification,” 2018. Available at: <https://kantarainitiative.org/download/7902/>.
- [137] International Organization for Standardization, “ISO/IEC 29184:2020, information technology online privacy notices and consent,” 2020. Available at: <https://www.iso.org/standard/70331.html>.

-
- [138] J. H. Betzing, M. Tietz, J. vom Brocke, and J. Becker, “The impact of transparency on mobile privacy decision making,” *Electronic Markets*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 607–625, 2020.
- [139] Cambridge University, “Transparencies.” Available at <https://www.cl.cam.ac.uk/~jac22/books/ods/ods/node18.html>.